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King's College London

The Russell Tribunal on Palestine

Conveying Activist Wisdom for Future Action

Patrick Timmer

Supervised by Dr. Maria Varaki

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

Master of Arts in Conflict Resolution in Divided Societies

31 August 2023

12,899 words

This dissertation is the sole work of the author and has not been accepted in any previous application for a degree; all quotations and sources of information have been acknowledged.

I confirm that my research did require ethical approval:

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Study Title: The Russell Tribunal on Palestine (2010-14): A Critical Analysis of Its Aims and Strategies

Minimal Risk Registration Number: MRSU-22/23-36043

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On behalf of the College Research Ethics Committee”

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Although it might not be cited much in what follows, *For the Love of Humanity* (2018) is what introduced me to peoples' tribunals and started me on the path that has led me to producing this dissertation. Thank you Ayça Çubukçu – your writing, perspectives, and reflections remain an inspiration.

I would also like to thank the Association of Commonwealth Universities and Stellenbosch University for the opportunity to go to Azania (“South Africa”) for an eight-day summer school on (among other things) apartheid, anticolonial resistance, transitional justice, settler colonialism, and structural racism while undertaking the research for this dissertation. I met so many bright and inspiring people, some of whom are named above. Crucially, my time at the Summer School led me to substantially rework my dissertation, I hope, for the better.

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Abstract

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The Russell Tribunal on Palestine was a peoples' tribunal convened in six sessions across North America, Europe, and Africa between 2010 and 2014 that sought to advance the Palestinian cause. This dissertation – a piece of insurgent research based primarily on eight semi-structured interviews with the Tribunal's activists – is an exploratory narrative account of the Tribunal that aims to convey some of the as-yet-unearthed practical wisdom of its activists to the wider Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement. In it, my interlocutors share some of their experiences, perspectives, and reflections on the Russell Tribunal on Palestine with me, deepening our understanding of what the Tribunal was – in terms of what the thinking behind it was, what it did for the activists involved, and how its organizational dynamics played out – and how it might be done differently in the future. As such, this dissertation gives us, as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists, tools to help us think even more expansively about how we can advance the struggle for Palestinian liberation today.

A Note on Terms

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In what follows, I use ‘Palestinian liberation activists’ to refer to all Palestinians actively struggling for Palestinian liberation, no matter what that entails for them. Conversely, I use ‘Palestine solidarity activists’ to refer to all non-Palestinians actively supporting Palestinians in that struggle.

I use ‘Palestinian liberation movement’ to refer to all of the individuals, collectives, and organizations who historically understood or currently understand themselves to be working towards Palestinian liberation – again, no matter what that entails for them. My use of the term encompasses a diversity of visions for what Palestinian liberation concretely looks like and a diversity of approaches for realizing those visions. It includes everything from grassroots initiatives to official diplomacy and everything from Palestinian-led initiatives in and/or beyond Palestine to solidarity actions led by non-Palestinians. Relatedly, I use ‘solidarity sub-movement’ to refer to the segment of the Palestinian liberation movement that is predominantly made up of non-Palestinians, mostly works beyond historic Palestine, and plays a supporting role in relation to the wider Palestinian-led movement.

Further, in what follows, I frequently use first-person plural pronouns (e.g., “we”) to refer to Palestinian liberation and Palestine solidarity activists (like myself). This is because they are the community that this dissertation is primarily geared towards. This may seem inappropriate to some since I address myself neither to the community of scholars within a particular academic field nor the imagined universal citizen, as is often the case in academic

writing. However, this is a deliberate choice that I've made as part of my commitment to doing insurgent research.¹ Adam Gaudry, a proponent of insurgent research, writes that:

Most research output is not directed at Indigenous peoples or communities... Insurgent research... must be increasingly directed at the Indigenous reader and written by an Indigenous author in a language people can understand. Its strategic use of "we" and "us" goes beyond simple rhetoric and comes to symbolize commonality, solidarity, and a respect for our common situations.²

Palestinians *are* an indigenous people³ – but that's besides the point. Gaudry's point is that research should be written primarily *by* and *for* those who it is written *about*, *with*, and *on*." This is a point that I have taken to heart.

¹ See Chapter 1 for more on this.

² Gaudry (2011), 120.

³ See, among others, Salamanca et al. (2012), 4.

Members of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine's jury stand, holding hands, at the District Six Museum in Cape Town in November 2011. From left to right: Antonio Martin Pallin, Cynthia McKinney, Stéphane Hessel, Mairead Maguire, Ronnie Kasrils, Alice Walker, and Michael Mansfield. Courtesy of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine.

What if we asked theory to do something else – to help us see openings, to help us find happiness, to provide a space of freedom and possibility?⁴

⁴ Gibson-Graham (2006), 7.

Writing about the Russell Tribunal on Palestine as an Outsider

This Dissertation, Its Aims and Its Research Questions

This dissertation is an exploration of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine (hereafter ‘the RToP’ or ‘the Tribunal’), a peoples’ tribunal held on three continents from 2010 to 2014 that sought to advance the Palestinian cause. It addresses the following research questions:

1. What *was* the Russell Tribunal on Palestine?
2. And how might it be done differently today?

At the same time, this dissertation is also a story about how I learned about the Tribunal from those involved in it.⁵ In the following pages, I shadow several RToP activists as they tell me about the Tribunal, share their experiences of it, and offer their reflections on it nearly a decade after its final session in Brussels ended. As they do so, they’ll help us get our hands on a richer, more multidimensional portrait of the Tribunal than the one we can get solely through its official documents, available video footage, and existing writing on it. They’ll help us better understand what the thinking behind the Tribunal was, what it did, and how a future people’s tribunal on Palestine might be done differently. In doing so, my interlocutors will give us – as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists – tools to help us think even more expansively about the pathways that we can and should pursue to advance the struggle for Palestinian liberation today.

⁵ I touch on why this story is important in Chapter 1 below.

The Russell Tribunal on Palestine: A Very Short Introduction

The Russell Tribunal on Palestine was launched at a press conference in Brussels on March 4, 2009. Its official documents explain that it was founded in response to two things: first, the non-implementation of the International Court of Justice's (ICJ) 2004 Advisory Opinion on Israel's Apartheid Wall⁶ in the West Bank (which found the Wall to be illegal, judged Israel to be obligated to dismantle it, and concluded that other States were obligated to not help Israel maintain it);⁷ and second, so-called Operation Cast Lead, Israel's violent 2008-09 military assault on the Gaza Strip. The Tribunal's documents also reveal that it sought to continue the work of the Russell Tribunals on Vietnam (1967) and Repression in Latin America (1974-75), two earlier peoples' tribunals.⁸ Pierre Galand, a key organizer of the Tribunal, stated that the RToP's aims were as follows:

to defend the rights of the Palestinian people, to denounce the international community's dereliction of duty and its complicity in Israel's failure to respect those rights, and to support activists in Palestine, Israel and throughout the world who call for the exercise by Palestine of the right to self-determination.⁹

As a peoples' tribunal, the RToP wasn't sanctioned by any States or international organizations. Nevertheless, it made significant use of law – legal reasoning, language, rules, standards, practices, and ways of being – to achieve its aims. For example, at each of the

⁶ 'Apartheid Wall' is a contested term. However, in my view, it is an appropriate one. As numerous scholars, human rights organizations, and UN reports have pointed out, the Wall is an integral part of Israel's institutionalized system of colonial and racialized segregation and domination in all of historic Palestine and beyond, amounting to a violation of the peremptory norm prohibiting apartheid. See, among others, Sultany (2022), Erakat (2018), 213-18, Muhareb et al. (2022), Amnesty International (2022), and UN General Assembly (2022). Of course, some scholars contest this – in my view, unconvincingly. See, for example, Zilbershats (2013).

⁷ International Court of Justice (2004), 136-203. See especially para. 163.

⁸ For a list of documentary sources published by these two tribunals, see the Bibliography in Byrnes & Simm (2018a).

⁹ Russell Tribunal on Palestine (RToP) (2014) [hereafter 'Brussels 2 Conclusions'], 5.

Tribunal's many days of public hearings, a jury of eight to ten members sat at a long table in front of an audience, hearing detailed evidence and testimony from a series of experts. Based on these hearings, the Tribunal made original legal analyses and formed legal judgments in response to the questions put before it with the help of a team of legal advisors. On the final day of each of its six sessions, the jury held a press conference presenting its conclusions, subsequently publishing them in writing.¹⁰ However, as a non-State-sanctioned initiative, the Tribunal obviously couldn't enforce these judgments in the way that a domestic court, at the very least, usually can.

The jury, which was slightly different for each session, was filled with high-profile individuals well-known for their stance against injustice. It included people like Angela Davis, the iconic American feminist, antiracist, abolitionist philosopher and activist, Stéphane Hessel, the French resistance fighter, World War 2 concentration camp survivor, diplomat, and human rights advocate, and John Dugard, the renowned South African law professor and former UN Special Rapporteur on Palestine.

The RToP held sessions on the complicity of the European Union, the United States, the United Nations, and transnational corporations in Israel's violations of international law, on the question of Israeli apartheid, and on so-called Operation Protective Edge, Israel's brutal 2014 military assault on the Gaza Strip.¹¹ In total, these sessions were attended by over 2,000 people.¹²

Among other things, the Tribunal concluded that "Israel's rule over the Palestinian people, wherever they reside, collectively amounts to a single integrated regime of

¹⁰ The RToP also published some of its documentary evidence. See RToP (2010b) and Winstanley & Barat (2011). Additional documentation can be found on the RToP website at <https://www.russelltribunalonpalestine.com/en/> (last accessed 19 July 2023).

¹¹ See RToP (2010a); (2010c) [hereafter 'London Conclusions']; (2011) [hereafter 'Cape Town Conclusions']; (2012) [hereafter 'New York Conclusions']; (2013); and Brussels 2 Conclusions.

¹² Online interview, RToP organizer, 26 June 2023.

apartheid”;¹³ that the UN is violating its own Charter and is criminally complicit in Israel’s violations of international law;¹⁴ and that Israel committed crimes against humanity and direct and public incitement to genocide during its 2014 “Operation Protective Edge.”¹⁵ Based on these conclusions, the RToP made several submissions to the UN Human Rights Council and gave presentations and speeches to two UN committees and the European Parliament.¹⁶

The Tribunal’s high profile, deliberate media strategy, and bold conclusions (when compared to the prevailing discourse on Israel among much of the so-called international community at the time) meant that it received a decent amount of coverage by both mainstream and alternative English-speaking media outlets.¹⁷ Occasionally, it also provoked heated public debate. For example, leading up to the Tribunal’s 2011 Cape Town session, Richard Goldstone, the South African judge responsible for the Goldstone Report (which examined violations of international law committed by both Israelis and Palestinians during “Operation Cast Lead”), published a piece in the New York Times criticizing the Tribunal from a Zionist standpoint.¹⁸ From a different angle, the Tribunal received public criticism from Palestine solidarity activists after its New York session in 2012.¹⁹

Overall, the RToP was a high-profile, timely, sizeable, and unique initiative within the history of the Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement. And, significantly, the Tribunal found a strong base of support within that movement: it was

¹³ See RToP, Cape Town Conclusions, paras. 5.44 and 5.45.

¹⁴ See RToP, New York Conclusions, para. 5.105.

¹⁵ See RToP, Brussels 2 Conclusions, paras. 12 and 24.

¹⁶ See UN International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (2012); UN General Assembly (2012a); (2012b); (2012c); (2013a); (2013b); and 2014. The Tribunal presented at the European Parliament on September 25, 2014.

¹⁷ Here’s a small selection: Ahmari (2012), Moor (2012), Adas (2013), Derry Journal (2014).

¹⁸ See Goldstone (2011).

¹⁹ See Greenhouse (2012) and Baskin (2012). For responses to these criticisms, see Meyer (2012) and Barat (2012).

ultimately endorsed by just under 300 grassroots collectives, coalitions, campaigns, and NGOs from around the world, including the Palestinian BDS National Committee – the leadership body of the global Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement.²⁰

A Refusal to Narrate

The preceding summary of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine is based almost entirely on available archival sources. It's also where my narration of the Tribunal in an authoritative, panoptical voice stops. In fact, I *refuse* to narrate the Tribunal in such a voice any more than I have already. In doing so, I'm inspired by the practice of 'ethnographic refusal' developed by anticolonial anthropologists such as Audra Simpson, Eve Tuck, and Wayne Yang (among others).²¹

I refuse to do so for two related reasons. Firstly, I lack lived experience, and thus standpoint knowledge, of the Tribunal: I wasn't involved in the RToP in any way. I didn't attend any of the many meetings of the Tribunal's International Organizing Committee, nor did I write any of the Tribunal's hundreds of pages of documentation and legal analysis. And secondly, I don't have 'permission to narrate' – to quote the title of an article by Edward Said.²² Those involved in the RToP haven't explicitly given me the authority, in any kind of procedurally-sound way, to tell *the* or even *a* story of the Tribunal on their behalf. Rather, I've taken the liberty, as an outsider, to write about the Tribunal at a time when there isn't a lot of writing on it out there already. In doing so, I've put myself in a position where it's easy for me to do harm to RToP activists by taking their story away from them. In order to hedge against this possibility, from this point on, I'll adopt a more self-reflective, quasi-autoethnographic voice. By doing so,

²⁰ Palestinian BDS National Committee (BNC) (2010). BNC representatives also presented at the RToP's Cape Town session.

²¹ See Simpson (2007) and Tuck & Wang (2014).

²² Said (1984).

I'll make more room for them to narrate their experiences and tell the story – or stories – of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine themselves.²³

However, one story that I *can* and *should* tell here is the one of my relationship to the RToP, how I came to write a dissertation about it, and how my project developed over time.

My Evolving Relationship to the Russell Tribunal on Palestine

Let me state at the outset that I'm not Palestinian – I've lived on Turtle Island (“Canada”) and in England my whole life, and I've never been to Palestine. I first learned about the Russell Tribunal on Palestine about a year ago (in the summer of 2022) while looking into peoples' tribunals, which I had just become aware of through reading Ayça Çubukçu's *For the Love of Humanity* (2018). That same summer, I also decided to start seriously reading up on Palestine. Up until that point, my knowledge of the nation was based mostly on conversations that I'd had with my partner and close friends, many of whom have Palestinian ancestry.

Because I had come to care even more deeply about Palestinian liberation through my summer reading, because peoples' tribunals continued to pique my interest, and because the RToP seemed to me to be ‘under-researched,’ I chose to write my dissertation about the Tribunal when it was time to finalize my topic in January this year. When I first began work on it later in May, I had a broad focus: I wanted to write about how and why the Tribunal was organized the way it was and how it could've been done differently. However, I soon felt pressure to narrow this scope, opting instead to focus on how it had engaged with law on account of the significant role that the latter plays in peoples' tribunals.

But this narrower focus never really sat right with me – and my conversations with RToP activists only served to increase that feeling. I was learning so much from them about

²³ I touch on autoethnography in Chapter 1 below.

many different aspects of the Tribunal, but if I continued to focus exclusively on the Tribunal's engagement with law, much of that learning would ultimately be excluded from my dissertation and left unshared. Yet at the same time, with tight space constraints to work with, I couldn't touch upon everything.

Around the time that I was experiencing this unease (in early July), I attended a summer school program in Azania ("South Africa"), where I deepened my awareness of extractive research and the coloniality of academia. This experience led me to reconsider my positionality in relation to both the RToP activists I was speaking to and the Tribunal as a whole. As a result of all of this, I substantially reworked this dissertation. I re-broadened its research questions so that I could touch on law but also move beyond it. Additionally, to better address my positionality and space constraints, I decided to write it more fully in line with the principles of insurgent research.²⁴

I can say for certain that the past four months of producing this dissertation have been transformative for me as an activist, researcher, student, and person. But that's enough about me – what's the value of this dissertation in the first place? What can an exploratory narrative account of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine add?

This Dissertation's Significance and How it Enriches the Existing Literature

The short answer to these questions is that this dissertation collects and conveys some of the activist wisdom of those involved in the RToP – wisdom that we, as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists not involved in the Tribunal, have not yet had shared with us but could benefit from.

The longer answer is as follows: as is self-evident, we should always be doing what we can to collectively learn about and from our past and ongoing activist and advocacy initiatives.

²⁴ More on this in Chapter 1.

This is so that we can best take stock of the avenues for action that are currently open to us and worth pursuing. Knowing this, when I started this research, I expected that there would already be a fair amount of publicly available writing – either in academic, policy, or activist spaces – on an initiative like the Russell Tribunal on Palestine. I expected that, as someone wanting to learn more about the Tribunal, I would be able to find work that would help me better understand what it was all about, what the thinking behind it was, why and how it was organized, what it did, and, perhaps, how it might be done differently today. I also expected that at least some of the activists involved in the Tribunal would’ve had the chance to collectively unpack and reflect on their efforts now that almost a decade has passed since the Tribunal’s final session.

However, what I found was that, while there was a decent amount of writing available on the RToP, much of it – while informative and insightful – was brief and/or introductory in nature. For example, in 2011, Victor Kattan – writing for Al-Shabaka, the independent Palestinian think tank – reviewed the findings and recommendations of the RToP’s Cape Town session on Israeli apartheid, concluding that they were “significant.”²⁵ In 2012, Frank Barat and Daniel Machover – both RToP activists – published a book chapter about the Tribunal where they introduced it, summarized the conclusions and recommendations of its Barcelona and London sessions, and briefly reflected on its importance and legacy.²⁶ Later, in a 2014 article, Binoy Kampmark used the RToP as a case study in order to advance a more general argument about the effectiveness of peoples’ tribunals.²⁷ And in 2018, Andrew Byrnes and

²⁵ Kattan (2011), 6.

²⁶ Barat & Machover (2012). Frank Barat was a key organizer of the RToP and Daniel Machover was one of its legal advisors.

²⁷ Kampmark (2014).

Gabrielle Simm highlighted the Tribunal’s tactic of focusing on transnational corporations in the introduction to their edited volume on the format.²⁸

Moreover, I also found that, aside from a few short passages in some of their books and articles,²⁹ the experiences and retrospective reflections of the RToP activists themselves had not yet been sought out and made available.

This all means that, to my knowledge, the kind of knowledge of the RToP that we, as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists, could use most – the “practically oriented and contextually bound” collective activist wisdom (in Sean Scalmer’s words)³⁰ that helps us better make concrete decisions about how to go about our activism in the present – has not yet been unpacked. Recognizing the potential value of this specific wisdom for us – and acknowledging that only RToP activists carry it – this dissertation enriches the existing literature about the Tribunal by conveying some of it to the wider Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement. In doing so, it deepens our understanding of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine and helps fill out our histories of Palestine solidarity activism, the Palestinian liberation movement’s engagements with law, and peoples’ tribunals.³¹

²⁸ Byrnes & Simm (2018b), 22-23, 33-35. Other works on the RToP include Lendman (2010) and Harlow (2013).

²⁹ See Reynolds (2016), 2112-13, Davis & Barat (2022 [2016]), and Falk (2017), chs. 5-7.

³⁰ Scalmer (2007), 48. Quoted in Reynolds (2016), 2109. See also Maddison & Scalmer (2006).

³¹ For histories of Palestine solidarity activism, see, among others, Thomson & Olsen (2023) for an overview of transnational Palestine solidarity initiatives from the 1950s onwards; Seitz (2003) on the evolution of the International Solidarity Movement; Bakan & Abu-Laban (2009) on the early history of the BDS movement; and Kouri-Towe (2015) on meanings and practices of solidarity within the queer Palestine movement.

For histories of the Palestinian liberation movements’ engagements with law, see, among others, Erakat (2018) on the Palestinian leadership’s engagements with law from the British Mandate to the present day; Allen (2021) on Palestinians’ engagement with investigative commissions from the British Mandate to the present day; and Dajani (2007) on the Palestinian leadership’s legal tactics during the Oslo peace process.

For histories of peoples’ tribunals, see, among others, Klinghoffer & Klinghoffer (2002) for a comparative study of the Reichstag fire trial, the Moscow show trials, and the Russell Tribunal on Vietnam; Byrnes & Simm (2018a) for an overview of numerous more recent peoples’ tribunals around the world; and Çubukçu (2018) for an ethnography of the World Tribunal on Iraq.

Unfortunately, situating the RToP within these three histories is beyond the scope of this dissertation. However, this work nevertheless helps highlight the diversity of the range of initiatives that belong to these histories.

Structure of the Dissertation

In the next chapter, I go over my data and methodology, discussing my commitments and how they inform this dissertation. I also explain what the sources of my data were, how I collected it, and some of the limitations of this work.

Chapter 2 is the empirical section of this dissertation – an exploratory narrative account of the RToP. In it, we'll learn from Tribunal activists about various aspects of it, such as: the appeal of the peoples' tribunal format; how the RToP built and strengthened activist networks across borders; the role that intergenerational differences played within it and how youth would play a bigger role in a future peoples' tribunal on Palestine; and how the Tribunal didn't make enough space for alternative understandings of international law to inform its tactics and how that space would be opened up more in a future peoples' tribunal on Palestine.

To conclude, I summarize the wisdom shared by my interlocutors and briefly consider how it might help inform the ways we, as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists, might move forward.

Data & Methodology: Insurgent Research Practice

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Although I began this project with some awareness of how research with people and communities can be extractive and cause harm to them,³² I came to heighten this awareness as my research progressed, ultimately choosing to embrace insurgent research. In this chapter, I'll say more about what this means for this dissertation. I'll also go over my data sources and collection methods. Further, as I go, I'll comment upon how this dissertation could've been improved with regards to data and methodology.

My Commitments and How They Inform This Dissertation

Adam Gaudry lays out insurgent research practice as follows:

Insurgent research is firmly grounded in an Indigenous resurgence ideology... It embodies four key principles:

1. Research is grounded in, respects, and ultimately seeks to validate Indigenous worldviews.
2. Research output is geared toward use by Indigenous peoples and in Indigenous communities.
3. Research processes and final products are ultimately responsible to Indigenous communities, meaning that Indigenous communities are the final judges of the validity and effectiveness of insurgent research.

³² See Smith (2021), chs. 2 and 3.

4. Research is action oriented and works as a motivating factor for practical and direct action among Indigenous peoples and in Indigenous communities.³³

Since most RToP activists weren't Palestinian (and hence weren't indigenous), doing this dissertation as insurgent research required some adaptation. As such, this dissertation is:

1. grounded in, respectful of and seeks to validate the perspectives and experiences of RToP activists, with priority to those who are Palestinian;
2. geared towards use by Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists;
3. ultimately accountable to RToP activists; and
4. meant to be empowering and intended to inform and stimulate action within the Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement.

One of the things this means is that, in this dissertation, I'm overtly political and explicit about what my goals and commitments are. As Gaudry writes:

Although many extractive researchers claim an objective, neutral, or unbiased stance, this type of conservatism has served only to mystify the workings of a reactionary and oppressive colonial system... Insurgent research should make no effort to hide a liberatory orientation.³⁴

It also means that I use a self-reflective voice inspired by feminism and autoethnography. Tony E. Adams, Carolyn Ellis and Stacy Jones write that one of the purposes of autoethnography is:

to show how researchers are implicated by their observations and conclusions... autoethnographic texts... align with feminist principles by revealing the ways in which these stories are produced; discussing the author's motivations for, and emotions in, writing;

³³ Gaudry (2011), 117.

³⁴ Ibid., 133. For a related discussion on partisanship and "guerilla intellectuals," see Reynolds (2016), 2109-11.

legitimizing “experiential and narrative ‘evidence’”; and claiming a “transformative or interventionist political stance”.³⁵

In line with this, I write with the ‘I,’ I’m transparent about how I came to write this dissertation, and I’ve structured it so that it reveals my own process of learning from the RToP activists I spoke to – thereby acknowledging and privileging their standpoint knowledge. Doing these things allows me to be more accountable to them and to respect the validity of their experiences, perspectives, and reflections (Gaudry’s first and third principles).

Doing insurgent research also means that I don’t ‘use’ the RToP as a ‘case’ in order, in the late David Graeber’s words, “to allow some academic to make a theoretical point or prove some rival’s theory wrong”.³⁶ Instead, this dissertation approximates ‘ethnographic writing’ as Graeber conceives it: writing “that aims to describe the contours of a social and conceptual universe in a way that is at once theoretically informed, but not, in itself, simply designed to advocate a single argument or theory” and in which “the general is in the service of the particular... Theory is invoked largely to aid in the ultimate task of description.”³⁷ As such, in this dissertation, I haven’t yet stated that I’m aiming to make a particular argument about anything – and I won’t. This is because, in my view, an exploratory, narrative account of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine that approaches it from several different angles would be more useful for us as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists than a theoretical argument using the Tribunal as a case study would be (Gaudry’s second and fourth principles).

³⁵ Adams, Ellis & Jones (2017), 4.

³⁶ Graeber (2009), viii.

³⁷ Ibid., vii-viii. For the related method of ‘thick description and weak theory,’ see Gibson-Graham (2014), S147-53.

Data Sources and Collection

With regards to data, this dissertation is based on archival materials and 8 semi-structured interviews with RToP activists conducted between May and July 2023.

My interviews with RToP activists lasted between 45 and 75 minutes and were all conducted online or by phone. I reached the activists that I spoke to either through their publicly available contact information or snowball sampling. Further, I ensured that they were able to fully determine whether and how they would be anonymized in the dissertation text – in what follows, some are fully identified by name while others preferred to remain unidentified. With their permission, two of the edited transcripts of our interviews are contained in the Appendices.

I also gave my interlocutors the opportunity to look over this dissertation before submission so that they could offer feedback to me and ensure that their voices were properly presented (Gaudry's third principle). However, unfortunately, due to time constraints, I was only able to give them a week to do so. This constitutes a limitation of this dissertation. However, after submission, I intend to meet with my interlocutors individually to get their more detailed perspectives, feedback, and criticisms of my work.

In line with insurgent research and solidarity activist practice, one of my top priorities during the interview process was to speak to Palestinian RToP activists. More generally, I made a deliberate effort to seek out as many different perspectives on the Tribunal as I could. To this end, I also consciously tried to speak with people who held different roles within the Tribunal, such as organizer, jury member, legal advisor, or presenter. Further, I tried to speak both to people involved with the Tribunal who are quite visible in the Tribunal's archival traces (e.g., official documents, video recordings, etc.) and those who are less so. Moreover, I made a deliberate effort to speak to women, people of colour, and individuals with non-conforming

gender identities and sexualities.³⁸ Finally, I consciously tried to speak to Israelis RToP activists.

Ultimately, I was able to speak to one Palestinian and one Israeli. Further, two of the activists I spoke to were people of colour, with the rest being white. Moreover, I was able to speak to one woman. Four of the activists I spoke to were legal advisors, two were organizers, one was both an organizer and a presenter, and one was just a presenter. The relatively small number of activists I was able to speak to limits the richness of the exploratory narrative developed in the next chapter to some extent.

Perhaps the biggest limitation of this dissertation, however, is that it could've been more participatory and co-creative. For example, I could've given the activists that I spoke to the opportunity to write parts of the narrative developed in the next chapter and I could've given them the chance to determine the agenda, aims and research questions of this dissertation. Had I done these things, I would've been more accountable to them and this dissertation would've been more geared to their priorities.

Be that as it may, I now turn to developing my exploratory narrative of the RToP, where we'll be able to learn from the experiences, perspectives, and reflections of the activists themselves. As I mentioned earlier, in it, we'll hear about the thinking behind doing a peoples' tribunal, how the RToP built and strengthened activist networks across borders, the role that intergenerational differences played within the Tribunal, and how it didn't open enough space up for alternative understandings of international law to inform its tactics. We'll also hear about how a future peoples' tribunal on Palestine would place youth in a more central role and ensure

³⁸ I made an effort to speak to women, people of colour, and individuals with nonconforming gender and sexual identities involved in the RToP for two reasons. Firstly, because such individuals, on account of their marginal positions, are often *both* more inclined to diverge from dominant perspectives *and*, despite this, not sought out for their perspectives, I wanted to ensure that I made space for their voices. And secondly, I wanted to be attentive to the possibility that such individuals might have experienced discrimination, harassment, and/or harm during their involvement with the Tribunal on account of their gender, race and/or sexuality – as we know still so often happens, even in activist and advocacy spaces today.

that more of a space would be opened up for new and alternative understandings of international law to be voiced and integrated into its tactics. Throughout, I'll add context and elucidations to what my interlocutors share.

Learning from the Activists

What the Peoples' Tribunal Format Offered

One of the first things that people tend to ask when I tell them about the Russell Tribunal on Palestine is: why a peoples' tribunal? As one RToP legal advisor remarked to me, this is the “perennial question” of peoples' tribunals. It was also one of the questions that I had coming into this project. By asking this, we seem to be trying to better understand what peoples' tribunals can uniquely accomplish in comparison to other kinds of activist initiatives, such as marches, petitions, conferences, blockades, and formal legal action – to name but a few.

When I asked this same legal advisor, who is now a law professor, how he would respond to this question, he began in this way:

But you know, there is this perennial question of why, if you are a social movement or an organization that's trying to do something that isn't a set of lawyers, why do it through the aesthetic or format of a legal court? And so there's a couple of interesting things. One is about the warranted or unwarranted supremacy or hierarchy that the law has, at least in the institutional viewpoint of many sites of power... the law has this authority or legitimacy that a different type of document or process won't have, right? So if you have a judgment from a court, that will carry more weight than a study, or a report, or a campaign, or whatever it is. So part of it is about simply being aware of and recognizing and understanding that, at least in certain circles, the law does carry this extra gravitas that other formats don't. We can talk about whether that's justified or warranted, whether we should be reifying that or not.

As he points out, the RToP organizers recognized that law has “extra gravitas” – it commands a kind of respect from people that other languages and frameworks don’t (“the warranted or unwarranted supremacy or hierarchy that the law has”). Consequently, they saw the peoples’ tribunal format as taking advantage of this way that people look up to law in order to get a hearing where (“in the institutional viewpoint of many sites of power”) other initiatives (“a study, or a report, or a campaign”) fall on deaf ears. This line of thinking is reflected in the Tribunal’s official documents, where it frequently takes pains to state that “Public international law constitutes the legal frame of reference of the Russell Tribunal on Palestine.”³⁹

He thus revealed to me here that the Tribunal was quite pragmatic in its tactical thinking. It acknowledged the *fact* – regardless of whether it was legitimate or not – that law enjoys a kind of special authority in the eyes of powerful institutions and many people living in the global North and around the world.⁴⁰ Accepting this reality, they opted for a format that would suit it.

Interestingly, this legal advisor conveys the thinking of the RToP organizers while simultaneously maintaining a critical distance from it. He leaves the door open to the possibility that law’s supremacy is unwarranted, and hence that it may have been better for an initiative like the RToP to challenge rather than legitimize that supremacy – or perhaps, to challenge it *while* legitimizing it.

Despite doing so, this legal advisor expressed to me that there was nevertheless a genuine benefit to strictly adhering to positivist international law:

So all of that is to say that yes, there was a benefit because, for better or worse, apartheid – you can always have comparative political analysis but the reason that I think it’s gained so much

³⁹ RToP, London Conclusions, para. 1.4.

⁴⁰ This supremacy of law is often referred to as ‘liberal legalism.’ See, for example, Allen (2021), 1-30, and Hunt (1986).

traction among these more mainstream advocacy organizations is obviously because it was dealt with legally through international treaties that prohibited apartheid, that criminalized it, and made clear that it was something that could happen beyond Southern Africa, it wasn't something that was confined to that history and you could have similar features of a system or a regime elsewhere, and if they ticked the boxes of what apartheid is, then that would be prohibited as apartheid. And so, for better or worse, the movement against apartheid from the 70s onwards was partly constituted through law, and that... gave a hook for the advocacy organizations and civil society organizations more recently to talk about that and apply that in the Palestinian context.

Here he refers to the fact, conveyed to me by several of the RToP activists I spoke to, that the Tribunal's analysis of and conclusions on Israeli apartheid were later taken up by mainstream human rights organizations such as Amnesty International.⁴¹ By making this reference, he shows that the RToP's pragmatic tactic of sticking to positivist international law did indeed allow it to be heard by institutional sites of power that would have otherwise ignored it had it engaged with law to a lesser extent or more "impudently."⁴² This is presumably because these sites of power need to stick to this legal framework themselves in order to protect their reputations as organizations of moral integrity.

Interestingly, he also reveals here that the RToP took inspiration from the anti-apartheid movement in Azania – specifically, the latter's recognition that it could bring the international legal system onto its side, without relying on it exclusively, to achieve its aims.

One final thing worth noting from these excerpts is that this legal advisor, like several of the other activists I spoke to, doesn't compare the RToP first-and-foremost to "real" tribunals – like dismissive critics of peoples' tribunals tend to do. One example of this is Richard

⁴¹ See Amnesty International (2022).

⁴² For an excellent overview of how political movements can use law, including in "impudent" ways, see Brabazon (2017).

Goldstone’s op-ed, mentioned earlier, where he criticizes the RToP on the grounds that “It is not a “tribunal.” The “evidence” is going to be one-sided and the members of the “jury” are critics whose harsh views of Israel are well known.”⁴³ Rather, my interlocutor finds it more useful to compare the Tribunal to things like marches, NGO reports, media campaigns, and policy analyses.

As I reflected on his preference later, I began to see the thinking behind the RToP’s deployment of the peoples’ tribunal format more clearly. As a publicized and performative initiative, it generated high visibility through collective outcry like marches and other mass demonstrations do. However, because such spectacular initiatives are often dismissed from the right as “a bunch of angry activists” presumed to be irrational and therefore wrong on account of their anger, the RToP combined public outcry with the rigor and integrity of NGO reports, legal scholarship and policy analysis – thereby anticipating such dismissive critiques.

To sum up, this legal advisor helped me – and might help us – better understand what the tactical thinking behind the Russell Tribunal on Palestine was. He shows us that the Tribunal was based on a calculated pragmatism that recognized and exploited the supremacy that law enjoys over other languages, frameworks, and standards in many global sites of power and for many people. He also shows us that this pragmatic approach proved its worth through the institutional access it granted to the Tribunal activists. However, at the same time, he leaves open the question of whether, despite its benefits, this pragmatic approach was the best one for the RToP to take. We’ll hear more from him on this later.

Strengthening Activist Networks and Learning from Each Other

While I certainly expected to hear from the RToP activists I spoke to about law, one thing that I admittedly didn’t expect to hear from them as much as I did was how impactful the Tribunal

⁴³ Goldstone (2011), A.27.

was for them in terms of personal growth, empowerment, and relationship-building. These impacts of the Tribunal are almost invisible to people who weren't involved in it, like me – they don't show up in the Tribunal's documents and video footage and haven't yet been publicly highlighted. Yet, for those I spoke to, they were incredibly important. It's therefore worth spending some time on them here.

One of the activists who emphasized the significance of these impacts in his conversation with me was Jeff Halper, an Israeli anthropologist, activist, and head of the Israeli Committee Against House Demolitions (ICAHD). Jeff was a member of the RToP's Support Committee and presented to the Tribunal in Cape Town. When, near the end of our conversation, I asked him whether there was anything else about the Tribunal that he thought was worth mentioning, such as any particularly memorable experiences, he said the following:

Well, I think one of the useful things as well, certainly for me, was the networking. A lot of us can be very isolated here... in terms of linking to other struggles, in terms of getting the input of international lawyers, linking up with a bigger body of supporters... So from the point of view of breaking our isolation, getting us in contact with others... these sessions were over two, three, four days. You're in hotels, you're going out for meals, you're hanging around... And then of course there was the follow-up that comes out of that. So that helped me a lot, I still have contacts from that time. And part of it also is that it served as a legitimization. We're a small group, ICAHD. All the other groups are fairly limited as well. So the fact that it gave us a certain visibility, a certain celebrity, even, within our little tiny circles, so that, after, when we spoke about issues, it maybe had more of a resonance... So in terms of empowering us, being a part of that process, and interacting with those people, was important... it was much more collaborative... we had a lot of people sitting down together, the jury, the witnesses, the organizers, really planning it all out and so on... And collaborative in the sense of linking us all up and spending time with each other... it's networking. Which is one of the things that the Tribunal did very well, because it was over a few days, and in different parts of the world.

Here, Jeff reveals how the RToP expanded and strengthened activist networks across borders. He mentions how grassroots organizations like his are “very isolated” – and how the Tribunal helped break that isolation by bringing people together from across national, topical (“linking to other struggles”), and vocational divides (“getting the input of international lawyers”) to collaborate with each other in a collective endeavour over days and even years. For context, the Tribunal drew parallels between and brought people together from across the Palestinian liberation movement, the anticolonial movement in Azania (as the legal advisor earlier highlighted), the Indigenous movements on Turtle Island (North America), the antiracist movement in what’s known as the United States, and the anti-globalization movement.⁴⁴ Additionally, it involved people from a wide range of professions, from lawyers, to authors, to union organizers, to grassroots activists.

Jeff also mentions how, by bringing activists together from across these divides to labour and get to know each other better over an extended period of time, the Tribunal legitimized and empowered these activists and their respective organizations – which it did by creating a space for them to recognize and validate each other’s work (“it gave us a certain visibility, a certain celebrity, even, within our little tiny circles”). In doing so, it enabled the activists to do their work more effectively once the Tribunal had ended (“so that after, when we spoke about issues, it maybe had more of a resonance”).

Importantly, he also reveals here that one of the consequences of the RToP bringing activists from varied backgrounds together was the wisdom and experience sharing that it encouraged by doing so. For example, Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists could learn from Indigenous activists involved in the American Indian Movement (AIM) and

⁴⁴ In Angela Davis’ words, the RToP recognized the “intersectionality of struggles.” See Davis & Barat (2022 [2016]), 18-20.

vice versa.⁴⁵ Likewise, some of the writers and grassroots activists involved in the RToP might have come to better grasp the technicalities of the Palestinian liberation struggle from a doctrinal legal perspective while some of the lawyers might have come to better appreciate it from a social-historical and personal perspective.

To sum up, by sharing his experiences with me, Jeff attuned me – and might attune us – to just how impactful the Russell Tribunal on Palestine was for the activists involved in it. By doing so, he helps us appreciate the role that the Tribunal played in building and strengthening the global Palestinian liberation movement in the early 2010s. And in fact, this was one of the unstated aims of the Tribunal from the outset. As one of its organizers told me: “the main aim was to reinforce, to give more tools to the movement.”

Intergenerational Differences, Institutionalization and Youth

Throughout my research, I was keen to hear from those I spoke to about how they thought the Russell Tribunal on Palestine might be done differently today. To this question, my interlocutors gave me a wide variety of interesting and insightful answers. For example, one RToP legal advisor told me that Tribunal “was not complete enough” and “could have been more precise in its conclusions.” Raji Sourani pointed out to me that the Tribunal should not be a “one-time recipe” and that “it’s very important to repeat it again and again, maybe in different areas, in different countries, for the new generation.”⁴⁶ Similarly, another Tribunal legal advisor helped me see that a future peoples’ tribunal on Palestine would involve the Global South more, telling me that “we could’ve gone even further then, having more of a

⁴⁵ The AIM is a grassroots Indigenous anticolonial movement in what’s known as the United States. It orchestrated some high-profile actions in the 70s. For more, see Banks (2005). Two AIM leaders were involved in the RToP: Dennis Banks and Russell Means.

⁴⁶ Raji Sourani is a Gaza City-based Palestinian lawyer, activist, former political prisoner, and co-founder of the Palestinian Centre for Human Rights. He was on the RToP’s Organizing Committee and presented at its Cape Town session.

Latin American and more of an Indian subcontinent content to just give it wider reach.” However, I unfortunately cannot delve into all of my interlocutors’ responses here. In this section and the next one, I’ll unpack just two of them.

The first one that I’d like to highlight began to surface when, in the course of our conversation, I asked an RToP organizer about whether the Tribunal had internal discussions about going further back than ’67 and what those discussions were like. For context, the Tribunal did indeed go back to ’48 and earlier in its Cape Town and New York sessions, but it didn’t do so in its earlier Barcelona and London sessions.⁴⁷ In his words:

... most people, or a lot of people, including Leila Shahid, who was the Palestinian Ambassador to Belgium and the European Union, were like “The PA is for two-states, so if we’re discussing two-states, we’re not discussing pre-67.” The idea is like ’67 borders and stuff. And that’s why the most heated discussions we had were about apartheid, because we wanted to include ’48, the refugees, the diaspora. So there was this... the biggest disconnect, if there was one, was between the old generation, Belgian senators and former Palestinian envoys and stuff, and the new generation, either European or Palestinian. The new generation was like “no, we cannot talk about Palestine without talking about the Nakba, ’48, pre-Nakba, the refugees.” And the older generation, because, in a way, they had been raised, they had been trained to think two-states for so long, wanted very much to focus on like, “we talk from ’67 onwards.” But anyway, I think this reflects the question of the whole movement, that the Palestine justice movement had at this point... And nowadays, with BDS and the apartheid analogy, this is long gone. Hardly anyone speaks about Palestine without mentioning the Nakba, the refugees, and stuff like that.

⁴⁷ In June 1967, Israel won an aggressive war against Egyptian, Syrian and Jordanian forces, resulting in Israel’s occupation of the Golan Heights, the Sinai Peninsula, the Gaza Strip and the West Bank, including East Jerusalem. See R. Khalidi (2020), ch. 3, and Masalha (1997). 1948 is the year that the beginning of the Nakba – the ongoing ethnic cleansing of Palestinians by Zionists – is generally pegged to. See R. Khalidi (2020), ch. 2, Masalha (2012), and W. Khalidi (1992). In what follows, I presume a basic familiarity with the history of Palestine. For an excellent overview, see R. Khalidi (2020).

The organizer – himself one of the younger activists – reveals here that there was, to some extent, a “disconnect” between the older generation and the younger generation within the Tribunal. As he mentions, some of the older activists were less inclined to diverge from the stance of the official Palestinian leadership. Relatedly, by virtue of their more diplomatically-oriented vocations and experiences, some of them had become accustomed to approaching the problem of Zionist (i.e., white Jewish supremacist)⁴⁸ settler-colonial domination in Palestine through the diplomatic lens of a ‘Palestinian-Israeli conflict’ entailing conflict resolution through a ‘peace process.’ For context, the internationally-mediated peace process, based on UN General Assembly Resolution 181 (partitioning Palestine) and UN Security Council Resolution 242, envisions two States in historic Palestine where one is fundamentally Jewish and settler – thereby legitimizing Zionist settler-colonialism and territorial conquest.⁴⁹ It also sidelines the right of return of ethnically cleansed Palestinians, especially for those ethnically cleansed before ’67 and from the territory now known as Israel.⁵⁰ All in all, the peace process essentially identifies Israel’s occupation of the Gaza Strip, the West Bank and East Jerusalem in 1967 to be where ‘the problem’ begins in historic Palestine – hence the insistence by some of the older activists that there was no need to go back further than that year.

On the other hand, as the organizer reveals, the younger activists felt that it was essential for the RToP to explicitly address pre-’67 Palestinian history – the British Mandate, the Partition, the beginning of the Nakba, and the legitimization of Israel. Having come of age post-Oslo, they didn’t have as much faith in the peace process framework as some of their older comrades – if they had any at all. They thus brought a different conception of “defending the

⁴⁸ See, among others, Erakat (2015) and B’Tselem (2021).

⁴⁹ For a brief overview of the problems with UNGA Res. 181, UNSC Res. 242 and the two-state framework, see Sultany (2022), 27-28. See also Cattani (2000), Dakwar (2007), Kattan (2009), and Erakat (2018) for more detailed discussions.

⁵⁰ For more on Palestinian refugees, see Albanese & Takkenberg (2020).

rights of the Palestinian people” to the table: one that necessarily included addressing Zionist settler-colonialism, territorial conquest, ethnic cleansing, and the denial of the right of return – and the roles of the UN, the EU, other States, human rights organizations, and corporations in sweeping it all under the rug.

Interestingly, as my interlocutor also noted to me here, this disconnect between younger and older within the RToP was the same one fragmenting the wider movement that the Tribunal belonged to in the early 2010s. Significantly, he also noted that, today, the Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement have largely adopted the standpoint of the younger RToP activists (“And nowadays... this is long gone. Hardly anyone speaks... without mentioning the Nakba, the refugees”).

For context, this is because a framework that goes beyond ’67 – and indeed, goes beyond ’48 – insists on the enduring relevance of the wrongs that were the colonization and Partition of Palestine, the initial and ongoing ethnic cleansing of Palestinians, and the expropriation of their land by Zionists with the support of the United Nations, Britain, and others. In doing so, such a framework charts a way forward that doesn’t compromise on justice for Palestinians as much as the ’67 peace process framework does.⁵¹ Further, while perhaps alienating for imperial powers, such a framework has historically underscored the struggle for Palestinian liberation’s similarity to other anticolonial struggles, thus building global, mass pressure on Israel, the United Nations, and its allies. For example, in 1975, the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO)’s endeavours to frame its struggle as an anticolonial, revolutionary one (with recourse to a framework moving beyond ’67) paid off when Cuba, South Yemen, Libya, Somalia, and Syria jointly spearheaded the drafting and passing of UN

⁵¹ See, for example, Tatour (2021) and Sultany (2022).

General Assembly Resolution 3379, which affirmed that “Zionism is a form of racism and racial discrimination.”⁵²

On account the younger RToP activists’ recognition of this, the organizer pointed out to me that a future peoples’ tribunal on Palestine would place younger activists in a more central role. In his words:

I think it would be different... it would be younger for sure... A lot of the organizing committee people were, maybe not 80, but 70, 75, 80, then you had a few 40-year-olds. But I think now the committee’s average age would probably be around 30 to 50 rather than 70 to 80.

At the same time, he emphasized that the older activists played essential roles within the RToP:

... you know, when you work on something like that, you need to take into account all expertise. You know, these people had been involved in Palestine for a lot longer than I was, for example. These people had another experience in Palestine, and the idea was to bring everyone together, and try to adapt, and to try to find consensus, and try to explain to them that maybe, the two-state solution was over, and maybe for them to tell us “yes, but what we did thirty years ago is still useful, because of this, this and that.” ... I remember, for example, the late François Maspero... or Stéphane Hessel as well.⁵³ I remember them being very open, maybe the most open, of everyone... François had been involved with like, Frantz Fanon, Che Guevara, like he had this amazing history. And very quickly they were very open to letting us speak, the younger generation. Me, Noura Erakat, Bina Ahmad, John Reynolds.⁵⁴ And when sometimes some

⁵² See UN General Assembly (1975) and Erakat (2018), 126-29. Unfortunately, this Resolution was revoked in 1991 as an Israeli precondition for participating in the 90s peace process, where the PLO opted to give up its anticolonial pre-’67 framework in the hopes of securing an independent Palestinian State. The consequence of this is that the Zionist movement is now more easily able to conflate legitimate criticism of Zionism and Israel with antisemitism – which only serves to underscore the importance of not giving up a pre-’67 framework.

⁵³ François Maspero was a French author, journalist, and co-founder of Éditions François Maspero. He was part of the RToP’s Organizing Committee.

⁵⁴ Noura Erakat is a Palestinian human rights attorney, law professor, activist, and co-founder of Jadaliyya. She was one of the RToP’s legal advisors. John Reynolds is an Irish law professor, activist, and co-founder of the Third World Approaches to International Law (TWAAIL) Review. He was also one of the RToP’s legal advisors. I introduce Bina Ahmad later on.

others were like, “hey, we’re the statesmen here! We know better.” ... I remember roundtables where maybe some people were like, “ok, John Dugard, what do you think?” ... and then there was me. And he went to the next person, without asking me... And I remember François or Stéphane, when it was their turn to speak, they’d say, “actually I’d like to hear what [the young organizer] has to say, or what Noura has to say.” So they were very, very aware that young people can know better sometimes, or are more astute to some of the things.

Here, crucially, he emphasizes that part of the thinking of the RToP was to bring a diverse range of Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists together in the hopes of making their differences productive toward the end of developing a more shared, unified position. This goes back to the network-building and collaborative learning that Jeff highlighted earlier. Specifically, my organizer interlocutor points out that, while the younger activists could help some of the older activists see the problems with the two-state framework, the older activists could help the younger activists appreciate what was valuable within the longer history of the Palestinian liberation struggle that the latter might not have been old enough to be familiar with in the same way.

He also points out that several of the older RToP activists were extremely aware of the value of making space for the younger activists – to the point that they would speak up when some of the other older activists didn’t give the younger activists an opportunity to voice their perspectives.

To sum-up, this RToP organizer helped me learn – and might help us learn – several things. First, he draws our attention to the fact that the most heated debates over the Tribunal’s tactics were driven by a split between the ’48ers and ’67ers, with the former generally being younger activists and the latter generally being older. At the same time, he attunes us to how institutionalization can sometimes work as a technique of power (who institutionalizes?) that protects and legitimizes Zionist oppression and violence – and draws our attention to the role

that it played in the RToP and the wider Palestinian liberation movement in the early 2010s. Crucially, he also shows us how the Tribunal, while animated by the split between '48ers and '67ers, simultaneously played a role in bridging that gap, building consensus around the '48ers position – although he also helps us see that the Tribunal might have been more effective in that regard. In addition, he reminds some of us younger activists of what we can learn from our more experienced comrades and gives some of us older activists exemplary role models for managing power dynamics between young and old, established and unestablished, in our organizing. Overall, this RToP organizer helps us see how generational differences have historically translated into diverging ideas about what an activist initiative for Palestine should address and how it should do so. With reference to how going back to '48 has now become the dominant approach within the Palestinian liberation movement, he also shows us why youth should play a more central role in a future peoples' tribunal on Palestine.

Deference to the Law and Law's Weaponized Blindness

The other response to my question about how the RToP might be done differently today that I want to highlight came from Bina Ahmad, an Ahmadi Muslim human rights attorney at the Civil Rights Corps, writer, activist, and legal advisor for the RToP's New York session. When I asked her to expand on some of her critiques of law that she'd mentioned in passing earlier in our conversation – and to touch upon how the RToP addressed or failed to address those critiques – she said the following:

There are many really noble principles that we cite to all the time for human rights, but if we take a step back and look at the creation of the UN post-World War 2 by the most powerful nations who won this global war, setting up this system that's not actually democratic – the Security Council is *not* democratic, it's just permanent members who rule over everybody else in the world, have final say on everything, that are actually binding resolutions unlike the

General Assembly... we have to take a step back and recognize that operating within this incredibly bureaucratic, incredibly powerful nation-State-built institution is not going to bring us revolution or liberation. It's just a system we're also stuck in and have to understand... And so I want lawyers and people to take that critical view of the law... and recognize that we can be so much more radical and creative than what the law gives us. We don't have to confine our minds to, "well this is what the law says." We can understand what the law says but also say "well this is also just messed up" ... just even having to use these international human rights principles, that shouldn't limit us in being able to call out all of the different forms of violence by the UN and by Israel. And I think it often does. Because we're confined into writing a legal brief and doing a legal analysis. So the Tribunal didn't have that space, and I think that was lacking, being able to say these critiques, like "we don't need the UN or other powerful actors and nation-States to tell us what's right and wrong, and what's right and wrong with what's being done to us, *we know it*. And we can say whatever we want, and the law shouldn't confine us." ... but I think that if we were ever to revisit it, I think that there's definitely a more radical political shift within the legal community that means that maybe there would be a space now if we were to do it again.

And later, when I asked her to imagine what the RToP might look like today, she returned to this point:

Definitely just bringing a more radical politics in, the critique about having to use a legal system in general that's not created by people but created by nation-states and powerful victors of war, really. Like, "what does that mean? And we don't want to confine ourselves to that." ... And yeah, just being more intentional about thinking outside the law, and focusing on the movement organising, and the people connections, and the radical politics that can come out of this, I think that would be another thing I would probably do.

In these excerpts from our conversation, Bina articulates a sharp anti-imperialist critique of the international legal system as one that – because it was created by powerful colonial and

imperialist States and continues to be developed by them – (1) serves to sanction and thus invisibilize certain forms of colonial and imperialist violence, enabling such States to continue to dominate others (“just even having to use these human rights principles, that shouldn’t limit us in being able to call out all of the different forms of violence by the UN and by Israel”) and (2) serves to fizzle out anti-imperial and anticolonial resistance by channeling it into a frustrating and depoliticizing bureaucracy. As a consequence of articulating this critique, Bina calls for “thinking outside the law,” suggesting that ordinary and marginalized people can and must insist on the integrity of their sense of right and wrong by calling out the forms of violence that they are subjected to that positivist law is blind to (“we don’t need the UN or other powerful actors and nation-States to tell us what’s right and wrong... *we know it*”). Simultaneously, she acknowledges the Marxist Approaches to International Law insight that political movements and organizations cannot *not* engage with positivist law (“It’s just a system we’re also stuck in and have to understand”).⁵⁵ Because of this, she advocates for activists to engage with positivist law, but in a way that is “so much more radical and creative” than is typical.

As she made this critique and drew out its consequences, Bina also revealed to me that the RToP didn’t free up enough space for activists to voice such critiques and incorporate them into the Tribunal’s tactical thinking. As a result, the Tribunal was “confined into writing a legal brief and doing a legal analysis” in a way that limited it in two respects. First, the Tribunal didn’t devote as much time and resources to “the movement organising, and the people connections, and the radical politics that can come out of this” – the network-building, collaboration, and wisdom-sharing that Jeff brought up earlier – as it could have. And second, while sticking to positivist international law had its merits (as the legal advisor showed us earlier), using such a tactic also meant that the Tribunal reproduced the weaponized blindness that this framework exhibits towards certain forms of violence – including the violence of this

⁵⁵ See, among others, Knox (2012), 223-24.

framework itself – in a way that inhibited the Tribunal’s ability to achieve its aim of defending the rights of the Palestinian people in some respects. At the same time, Bina quickly pointed out to me that a future peoples’ tribunal on Palestine would open this space up more, thereby addressing these limitations.

To get a concrete example of Bina’s point about positivist international law’s weaponized blindness, I had to recall my conversation with the RToP legal advisor from earlier. Here’s the example he gave me then:

... but there also is this question again of the way that the law sometimes can operate as an obstacle to this more holistic, structural, and comprehensive analysis. Because one of the issues... is that settler colonialism, for a lot of people, makes most sense in understanding the history of conquest in Palestine... more so than, “what does international humanitarian law say, what does human rights say, or what does the two state solution say,” etc... and also in informing what the process should be from here, which is around decolonization and so on, rather than peace agreements or conflict resolution or conflict management... But, the issue with international law is that... settler-colonialism... is kind of legitimized and normalized, and that sovereignty and those territorial conquests are accepted and established. And so, where you have a movement or campaign or initiative that is defaulting or deferring to international law as its reference point, it obviously has to work within the limitations of what international law says... But the reality is that, if you’re talking about it from a doctrinal lawyers’ point of view, there’s no substance in terms of a legal rule or norm that you can use to say, “well Israel was established as a settler-colonial state, and that was a breach of international law at the time, and so we have to revisit that...” And so you’re defaulting to the law, you’re also limiting yourself in terms of what frameworks and language you can use.

As he points out, positivist international law legitimizes and invisibilizes pre-1960 settler-colonization as a form of violence.⁵⁶ Consequently, it also legitimizes and invisibilizes post-1960 settler-colonial violence emanating from pre-1960 settler-colonization. Therefore, as he alludes to, because the RToP stuck to positivist international law, it struggled to bring Zionist settler-colonialism into the centre of its analysis and couldn't explicitly call the latter out as both a fundamental wrong and an ongoing, unaddressed form of violence that the UN, the EU, third-party States, and people around the world are obliged to end.

Yet, as he noted to me, for many Palestinian liberation and Palestine solidarity activists, settler-colonialism is *the* framework for understanding the historical and contemporary situation in Palestine and for charting the path to liberation. It also happens to be the elephant that the Zionist movement has quite successfully kept in the closet over the years in order to protect the 'fruits' of its settler-colonial project.⁵⁷ To return to what Bina said, by not creating enough space for critiques of international law to be voiced by RToP activists, and by consistently deferring to positivist international law as a result, the Tribunal was somewhat out-of-tune with a widely shared framework for understanding and thinking about Palestine among activists in the Palestinian liberation movement. In addition, it arguably missed an important opportunity to help bring the aforementioned elephant out of the closet by more strongly challenging the UN, the EU, third-party States, international human rights organizations, and people around the world to reframe their understandings of the historical and contemporary situation in Palestine around Zionist settler-colonial domination expressed as apartheid – and anticolonial resistance to it.

⁵⁶ The UN Declaration absolutely prohibiting all forms of colonial domination dates to 1960. A fundamental principle of international law (like most domestic law worldwide) is non-retroactivity, expressed in the maxim "no crime without law." Israel was legitimized as a conventional nation-State in 1949 and therefore has not violated this prohibition from a positivist doctrinal point of view.

⁵⁷ See, among others, Hawari, Plonski & Weizman (2019).

To sum up, Bina, with the help of the other RToP legal advisor, helped me see – and might help us see – how the Russell Tribunal on Palestine’s adherence to positivist international law was, in some respects, limiting. Further, she helps us see that the Tribunal was limited in this way because it didn’t open enough space up for its activists (and perhaps its younger activists in particular, as the RToP organizer showed us earlier) to voice conceptions and critiques of international law that challenged more prevalent liberal conceptions, thereby making it difficult for these activists to influence the Tribunal’s choice of legal tactics in order to better address such limitations. Finally, she helps us recognize that a future peoples’ tribunal on Palestine should both integrate such alternative, critical conceptions of international law into its legal tactics more thoroughly and ensure that space is always available for the latest critiques and understandings of law to be voiced and put to work.

Summing Up and Ways Forward

In the preceding chapter, I was only able to highlight a fraction of the activist wisdom that Jeff, Bina, Raji and the other RToP activists I spoke to over the past few months shared with me. Nevertheless, doing so has helped us better understand what the Russell Tribunal on Palestine was and think about how an initiative like it might be done differently in the future.

To quickly summarize the wisdom that my interlocutors have shared, the RToP legal advisor helped us see how the Tribunal used the peoples' tribunal format as part of the pragmatic tactic of taking advantage of the special authority that law has in many institutional sites of power and in the eyes of many people around the world. He also showed us how this tactic generated concrete gains for the RToP, and the Palestinian liberation movement as a whole, with reference to Amnesty International's report on Israeli apartheid.

Jeff Halper attuned us to the role that the Tribunal played in strengthening the global Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement in the early 2010s, thus achieving one of its principal aims. He helped us see that it did so by bringing activists together from across physical, topical and vocational divides to collaboratively work and get to know each other better over an extended period of time. By doing so, as he showed us, the Tribunal enabled activists to share their wisdom and experiences with each other, legitimize and empower each other in their work beyond the Tribunal, and build power as a movement.

In addition, the RToP organizer showed us how the Tribunal was animated by a generational disconnect between the younger activists, who were generally inclined to insist that the Tribunal go back to '48 and beyond (the dominant view within the global Palestinian liberation movement today), and the older ones, who were generally inclined to stick to the

dominant peace process framework of proceeding from '67 onwards. He also showed us how this was partially because of how some of the older activists were less inclined to depart from the peace process framework on account of their many years of diplomatic experience. Furthermore, he attuned us to how the Tribunal nevertheless played a role in bridging this disconnect running through the entire Palestinian liberation movement during the early 2010s. In addition, he showed us why youth should and would play a more central role in any future peoples' tribunal on Palestine.

Finally, Bina Ahmad showed us how, because the RToP didn't open enough space up to consider new, alternative understandings and critiques of international law, it ended up sticking to positivist international law in a way that prevented it from doing as much as it could have to, among other things, (1) call out Zionist settler-colonialism as an ongoing and unaddressed form of violence and (2) challenge many institutional sites of power and people around the world to reframe their understandings of Palestine around Zionist settler-colonialism and Palestinian anticolonial resistance. Further, she showed us why a future peoples' tribunal on Palestine should and would open such a space up better, adopting tactics that better addressed such limitations.

So, how might these activists' wisdom concretely help us, as Palestine solidarity and Palestinian liberation activists, move forward today – at a time when there are doubts about whether the Palestinian leadership's attempts at legal action at the ICJ and ICC can really materially advance the struggle for liberation?⁵⁸ When the British government is currently introducing an anti-boycott bill aimed at taking the wind out of the sails of the BDS movement?⁵⁹ When Israel is currently engaging in 'spyware diplomacy,' selling spyware to foreign governments (for use against their own citizens) in order to develop economic links

⁵⁸ See Erakat & Reynolds (2021).

⁵⁹ See UK Government (2023).

with them, thus making them less likely to stand up for Palestinians?⁶⁰ When the global Zionist movement has quite successfully weaponized the definition of antisemitism to further shield itself and its settler-colonial project?⁶¹ When, alongside all of this, Zionist settler-colonial domination continues in and beyond historic Palestine?

Clearly, in response to these questions, my interlocutors' wisdom reminds us to continue to empower youth (especially Palestinian youth) and make space for them to play significant leadership roles in our initiatives. Their wisdom also reminds us to take alternative and unconventional perspectives and viewpoints seriously when we develop and hone our strategies and tactics, and to always strive to do so by consensus (since majority voting might lead to less prevalent perspectives being ignored). Additionally, their wisdom reminds us not to underestimate the importance of building (and *maintaining*) relationships of mutual care with each other across borders and all other kinds of divides – and to always strive towards a shared strategy and analysis of our situation, acting in coordination with each other in order to present as unified a front as possible.

More specifically, however, my interlocutors' wisdom also shows us how the peoples' tribunal format, with its investigative integrity, transparency, visibility, and base of popular support and involvement, can help us outflank and thus put pressure on larger powerholders such as mainstream human rights organizations, States, and international governing bodies. This is because we can use such initiatives to pre-empt and set a precedent for subsequent inquiries, tribunals and reports commissioned by powerholders (as the Russell Tribunal on Palestine did, especially with its 2014 Brussels session on “Operation Protective Edge”). We can also use them retrospectively as a way of levelling a critique against and pointing out the

⁶⁰ See Dadoo (2022) and Visualizing Palestine (2022).

⁶¹ See Aked (2023) and Winstanley (2023).

absurdity of existing judgments and inquiries.⁶² Would a pre-emptive peoples' judgment mirroring the ongoing ICJ and ICC investigations be an effective way of pressuring these judicial bodies to take positions that are more conducive to Palestinian liberation? And might a peoples' judgments toolkit containing rewritten passages of existing human rights reports and legal decisions – such as, for example, B'Tselem's 2021 report on Israeli apartheid⁶³ – be an effective way of both reframing the discourse around Palestine and doing popular legal education?

At the same time, my interlocutors' wisdom reminds us that engaging with law in the interest of furthering Palestinian liberation necessarily entails acknowledging, spreading awareness of, and *actively resisting* the ways that the international legal system has worked and currently works to enable the ongoing oppression of Palestinians and stifle their liberation. In my view, our future legal initiatives can, and indeed need, to take the liberty of occasionally departing from positivist law (at the points where it serves to protect and legitimize forms of domination) in order to insist upon using law as it should be *today*. Further, we can and should constantly be making a compelling case for why doing so is just – and many of us already are. By doing these things, we can establish deeper connections with other movements endeavouring to transform legal systems around the world (e.g., the abolitionist movement) while also ensuring that we are not compromising our cause by taking the positivist international legal system as the embodiment of justice.

And finally, their wisdom suggests to us that peoples' tribunals can be a useful way of building and globalizing the Palestine solidarity sub-movement. As Raji Sourani and several

⁶² This would be similar to what 'feminist judgments' do – they rewrite existing judgments that are lacking on account of sexism, homophobia, transphobia, racism, capitalism, etc. In doing so, they point out how such judgments, and the legal systems that produce them, actively perpetrate structural violence and injustice. Feminist judgments are thus a powerful form of both protest and popular education and conscientization. For an introduction, see Hunter, McGlynn & Rackley (2010).

⁶³ For an incisive critique of this report, see Tatur (2021).

of the other RToP activists I spoke to rightly pointed out to me, such initiatives can and should be done, when possible, in as many different parts of the world as is possible. In my view, local Palestinian liberation and Palestine solidarity activists should always be empowered to organize and lead such initiatives, and the latter should address localized topics relevant for Palestinian liberation – such as, for example, the relations that a particular State, municipal government, or local corporation has had and/or currently has with Israel and the Zionist movement. Peoples’ tribunals done in this way would, I think, empower those involved by both enabling them to deepen their expertise on issues relevant to Palestine and creating a space for them to reach their own conclusions about the topics being addressed. Furthermore, by virtue of the collaborative nature of peoples’ tribunals – which I think should be emphasized as much as possible – such initiatives could play an important role in building and strengthening more localized communities of Palestinian liberation and Palestine solidarity activists. In addition, as with any peoples’ tribunal, the conclusions resulting from such localized tribunals could be used to put pressure on local powerholders. However, if such localized tribunals are to be feasible, we have to figure out how we they can be done more cheaply.

Ultimately, these reflections and suggestions are only a few among many. My hope is that this dissertation will help inform and stimulate conversations across the Palestinian liberation movement and solidarity sub-movement, provoking many other thoughtful ideas and suggestions for imagining new ways forward to witness Palestinian liberation #WithinOurLifetime. For a Free Palestine!

Interview, Jeff Halper, June 8, 2023

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P: As you know, I was trying to get a sense of what your experience was like taking part in the Russell Tribunal. I know that you gave a presentation in Cape Town, but you were also, if I'm not mistaken, part of the Support Committee. I was wondering if you could start off by saying a little about what your involvement was, and what it meant to be a patron and a presenter.

JH: Well, I wasn't a central figure. It was kind of the Frank [Barat] show. We worked with Pierre [Galand] in Brussels. They sort of worked together. So I wasn't a central actor in the whole thing, I gave them support for the whole thing. Here and there I helped Frank makes some contacts, but I spoke at Cape Town, and I was also present at the session in New York, although I didn't speak there. But I was there, I happened to be in New York at that time. And then I worked with Frank on the summary of the whole thing, putting it all together. Especially the Cape Town piece of it. So I can't say that I was really a central actor.

... So, anyways, I thought that – the idea of course is excellent, you know. And it was sort of a replay of the Russell Tribunal on Vietnam, and so on. I thought what was good about it was that it was one of the first big international events that used the concept of apartheid. Apartheid was in the air – Jimmy Carter referred to it in his book back twenty years ago. I've talked about it and other people have – and now of course, since the Amnesty [International] report and, in the last couple years, Human Rights Watch and the UN – but at that time, it wasn't used so often. So one of the Tribunal's contributions was to bring that term into the political discourse. So that was important. And of course, in all the different meetings they really had excellent people. New York dealt more with indigenous voices – they had Native Americans there, they had Black Americans – you know, they had a lot of indigenous and

supposedly marginal voices. But ours dealt with apartheid. So I was there in Cape Town, with the others that I know, Shawqi Issa, a Palestinian, and many others. And there was the committee. And – you’ve probably seen what I’ve said – I talked about apartheid, and the fact that Israel, in fact, accepts the idea of apartheid. I mean, it conceives of its own system of apartheid – it just uses the term in Hebrew, which is *hafrada*, meaning separation. The name of the Wall is the ‘Separation Barrier,’ not the ‘Security Barrier.’ So Israel, in fact, accepts that, and it realizes, and it knows upfront about the fact that it’s an apartheid system. It simply says it in Hebrew, and so Israelis don’t really connect *hafrada* with apartheid. And of course, the rest of the world doesn’t know what *hafrada* means, so in a sense, it’s accurate but it didn’t come out. So that was one of my contributions.

P: Yeah, that was interesting, I picked up on that when I watched your presentation... I was wondering – how did you come to be involved with the Tribunal in the first place; did people reach out to you asking to participate?

JH: Look, I’ve been involved with this for many years. And I’ve been in the Israeli peace movement in general for fifty years. But for the last twenty-six years, I’ve been the head of the Israeli Committee Against House Demolitions [ICAHD], which is really one of the central groups here dealing with resistance to the occupation, especially focusing on house demolitions, but, you know, we’re political. So we’ve always tried to use the house demolition issue as a vehicle for getting at the bigger – “what does it mean, demolishing this family’s house? What are Israel’s intentions? And why is it doing it? And where is Israel going with all of this?” So it leads us – I’m an anthropologist, by profession. We always go back and forth between the micro and the macro. What’s happening on the ground is simply, literally, grounding your analysis. You’re dealing with reality, but then what does it mean? And then we go from there and extrapolate into the bigger, in my case, political situation. And that’s why [ICAHD’s] analysis is so good because it’s not just an opinion of someone whose read a million

books. It's based on being there on the ground, and if there's a contradiction between our political views and what's happening on the ground, then something's wrong. And if there's a contradiction between what Israel's saying – “we want peace, negotiation,” all that – and what it's really doing on the ground, then you've gotta go with what's happening on the ground. In other words, on the ground is really the check about “are you on the right direction; is your analysis good?” And so on. So I've been involved with that for many years, and I've written a number of books and been out speaking a lot. So I got to know Frank – Frank interviewed me before in London once. So he turned to me and asked me to be involved.

P: And could you tell me more about the reasons why you got involved?

JH: Well, that gets to what you're interested in, you know, about strategy. You see, we are political. Our goal at ICAHD is to actually end this whole thing. It's not just to protest, or resist, or educate, or advocate, or lobby, or campaign, but actually to be a political actor, as Israelis. And we call ourselves the Israeli Committee because we're taking responsibility for demolitions, we're also saying that as Israelis, we have to play a role in this whole thing. And we've always worked very closely with our Palestinian partners. So that's really important. We could never do work on the Occupied Territories without the Palestinians. But this is really the issue, where it gets into – you know, there's a concept of ‘civil diplomacy.’ The problem is that we on the ground, whether you call us activists, or civil society, actors, or whatever – we have no power, we're not elected, we don't have financial power, we don't have any political clout. And so governments are the ones that are making the decisions. Making the policies, the decisions, without any contact with us, obviously. We're completely ‘extrapolitical.’ Extraparliamentary.

So the big question, then, is, ok, how do civil society actors like us, or Palestinian civil society groups, how do we influence policy, government policy? What is the strategy? How do

the outside groups – we’re not going to get inside in any way, but how can – and so, we learned a lot of this from the African National Congress in South Africa. They had the same situation. And basically, the strategy that we talked about all these years, and that the Russell Tribunal on Palestine personified, was that, you have to mobilize international civil society. International civil society could be a very effective political actor. Human rights groups, and political groups, and trade unions, and churches, and other kinds of religious organizations, and civic organizations, universities, students – there’s a whole panoply of civil society actors. And so the question is, how do you mobilize them? But before you can mobilize them, you need a political plan. At that time, we didn’t have a political plan. We all knew that the two-state solution was gone, we knew that Israel was instituting an apartheid regime, but we had no – and, in a way, we still have no – political program that we can say to all our international supporters abroad, “this is what we want you to advocate for. When you go to parliament, and they ask you, ‘what do you want,’ this is the plan.” Because the Palestinians themselves haven’t gotten behind a plan yet. So, this is where it’s led to, in a way: [ICAHHD] is part of a new organization called the One Democratic State Campaign. And we’re saying that it has to be one democratic state, and we have a Ten Point Program...

So anyways, that’s really where you have to go. Until the Palestinians, and then with our support, a critical mass, get behind a political plan, we can’t really mobilize the international grassroots. And then from their point of view, they can’t really change government policy because we don’t have an end game. South African always had an end game. “One person, one vote.” We don’t have that. So the Tribunal then, in my view, was in that direction. On the one hand, we’re informing and empowering civil society around the world. It gives us a voice that we would never have in some kind of mainstream forum – government, media, universities, etc. So we would never have that voice, and that was important. It brought together some very influential people. But at the same time, I think that by getting us together and

articulating this, it helped us to begin to formulate some political ideas, certainly the idea of apartheid, which was then taken on by Amnesty and other human rights groups and the UN. I think that it kind of got kickstarted to some degree by our part of the conference. So that's where I think the significance is: how does civil society become a political actor?

P: And I guess my question, then, would be – just in your understanding of course – what was the appeal of the peoples' tribunal, or civil society tribunal format? As opposed to other things, like just having a series of public events, or discussion, or forums?

JH: I mean, it was structured as a tribunal. Obviously, it didn't have the official power, the formal authority, of a human rights tribunal convened by the UN, or whatever. It didn't have that, but nevertheless it had the idea of a tribunal that goes back to the original Russell Tribunal. You know, it's a very powerful idea. It's more than a workshop. It's really saying, "we really have to take a position here." Then what they did of course, is set up the Tribunal of very prominent human rights lawyers, very prominent public figures. So the Tribunal itself was really a body that couldn't be dismissed. This isn't just a bunch of political activists getting together like you might have at a workshop. And the idea was that you *do* get to a conclusion, even a legal conclusion, that you can then take forwards to the UN, to a court, or to a human rights body, or so on. So the idea was that this really is a body that can judge. That can make accusations. That can back up accusations. And that has more than a moral authority. I mean these people on the Tribunal were really respected academics, legal figures, political figures that just couldn't be ignored. So I think that it had much more power, and that was intended. A workshop doesn't have any agenda besides discussing an issue. This said upfront, "we are condemning this occupation which is illegal, and this and this and this and this are the ways that it is illegal, and this is what has to be done, and so on." So from my point of view it was really a much more powerful and appropriate kind of organization than just having a conference or something.

P: Yeah, that really gets to what the thinking was, so that's very helpful. Another thing that I wanted to ask you about was – they addressed several topics, apartheid, EU complicity, corporate complicity, US & UN complicity – just based on your familiarity with the Tribunal, do you feel like those were the right ones to talk about? Or do you feel like there were other topics and angles that might have been left out, that might have been worth speaking about as well? Obviously, I know that there were constraints with time and resources...

JH: Well, I don't know, it's hard to say because there are so many things that could have been talked about. I think in a way, it was interesting because the Tribunal wasn't the initiative of the Palestinians. It was the initiative of kind of the international body that consulted with Palestinians. So in some ways its role wasn't to bring up Palestinian suffering, oppression or whatever – its focus was on Israel, as the occupying power, as the apartheid regime, and so on. So, in a way, there's a lot of issues that it could have dealt with, like house demolitions – I mean there's a million human rights violations going on here. But I think its focus – and it's good that it had the focus – our part of it at least, or really all the way through – was on Israel. The basic question was, "how does Israel get away with this?" That was one of the questions. And then the second question was, "well what do we do about it? We know that they're getting away with violations of international law, and so on, so what do we do about it?" I think part of it was also – and this is significant – you know, the weakness of international law, we always talk about the 'human rights approach,' which I don't believe in at all, I think international law is bullshit, to tell you the truth. It's wonderful, I mean, the texts are wonderful, the scope is wonderful, and the intentions – and it's international law, you know, it *is* law! It has the authority of law, it's passed through the UN system. But it has no enforcement whatsoever. In 2006 [sic] the International Court of Justice in the Hague said that the Israeli Wall is illegal, has to be dismantled. The General Assembly accepted that ruling, and nothing happened. There's no enforcement. So, I think that in a way, the Tribunal was an attempt to call out this

gap between the corpus of international law and the fact that it really has no effect on the ground. Unless you take weaker people, you know, you take a Milošević, you take a Taylor, you take Saddam Hussein, you take Bashir – but you’re not going to bring Putin, or Netanyahu, or Biden, or any of these. And that’s the problem with it.

So I think the Tribunal kind of inserted itself into that middle level and really challenged the UN and international system saying “look, these are the violations.” Michael Mansfield, who was one of the prominent law people – that’s authority. Bring these voices of authority to say, “we’ve documented the violations. What are you going to do about it?” And going back to that question which was really the Tribunal’s challenge: why is Israel getting away with this? And in a more public way. Because when you have discussions of the Human Rights Commission in Geneva and so on, they’re not public so much, you know, there’s records – but this is really bringing it out in a public forum, and the fact that it’s a Tribunal, again, brings in a dramatic element – you know it was partly performance, too. To have Angela Davis presenting in front of a tribunal, you know, that has a dramatic aspect to it that I think was useful. So from that point of view, in a sense the issues that it tackled were maybe even less relevant than the fact that they were actually just attacking this whole system that’s allowing Israel to do what it did. But in general I think it covered the issues in a fairly comprehensive way. I wouldn’t have much criticism of the issues that were covered.

P: One thing that was interesting was that you said that the Tribunal asked itself this question of how Israel gets away with this, and it seems to me that the first part of an answer to that from the Tribunal was, ‘well because the EU and the UN and the US and a bunch of third-party states aren’t putting the pressure on Israel that they’re obligated to under international law.’ But then, to me, that raises another question: “how then does the EU and the UN and the US get away with not putting the pressure on Israel that they are theoretically legally obligated to?” And I was wondering, from your perspective, whether the Tribunal had any answer to that

question... What could the Russell Tribunal do to put pressure on the EU, US and UN beyond reminding them that they have certain legal obligations?

JH: I don't know if I'm answering your question, but it's a challenge to the refusal of the international community to enforce its own laws. These aren't laws that leftists in civil society made up – we all have human rights, and apartheid is a crime, etc. – these are laws that the UN, that the governments that are represented at the UN accepted as international law, it's their rules! What Biden always talks about, the 'international rule of law', and all that bullshit. So in a sense we're kind of calling *them* – saying, "wait a minute, why aren't you enforcing your own law? And, to get very specific, *these* are the violations of international law that Israel is committing and why aren't you holding Israel accountable?" And that's the problem, that's about as far as civil society can go. You see, the game is – and it's a game – the game is that governments pursue their own interest. It's *realpolitik*. International law has no standing whatsoever. If you can use it – for instance, against Saddam Hussein – for your own *realpolitik* reasons, then fine. Great, it's an instrument we can use. But as an instrument of justice? I mean, human rights are *ridiculous* to governments. Jimmy Carter was laughed out of office because he tried to base American foreign policy on human rights. Didn't do very well. So that's sort of the bad faith in the international system: governments claim that there's an international rule of law. Biden talks about it every day. But there isn't. And they would never accept international rule of law. They have the power – you can think about it this way. You're living in London, and there's laws, and you have police that enforce the laws. But you have this situation: if the law begins to threaten the interests of powerful people, they have the power to simply ignore the law. And that's what the international system is. Who's going to enforce it? Who's going to sanction the United States? Who's going to sanction Israel? So Israel knows, and everybody knows – it's like the Leonard Cohen song – everybody knows that Israel's violating it. They don't need the Tribunal to tell them that. But the question is, why aren't you *enforcing* the laws?

And that's where the bad faith comes in. The Tribunal's purpose was to call this bad faith out, to put it in the face of the governments. But that's the limit you have. You can't embarrass governments, really. You can't force them. Civil society has no way to really – and the Russell Tribunal, I don't think it had the ability to change public opinion in a major way. It was chipping away. It was part of the process of trying to change public opinion. But it lacked that kind of power. So we're living in a system of bad faith. And that's why civil society doesn't have the clout that it should. And by the way, it's not only governments, because the Russell Tribunal also concentrated, obviously, on corporations, too. So the focus was good in that it expanded the international system to include corporations.

P: So, going back to your analysis of international law and the international system as *realpolitik*, was the use of international law as a framework by the Russell Tribunal, as you understand it, was that limiting in any way?

JH: Well, yeah, but that's what you got. There's no other way, if you're talking about injustice, and oppression, and human rights, the only framework, the only language you have, is international law. In other words, governments have alternatives, they have the alternative of force. My BA's in Political Science. The first thing you learn is that States have a monopoly over the use of force. Only States can declare war. Only States can negotiate, sign treaties, so they have that monopoly. And that's what gives them that power that we don't have. We can't, for example, sit down with Palestinians and Israelis as civil society and negotiate some kind of peace agreement. It'd be an exercise. It's been done in a way, the Geneva Initiative they have here, but again it's just a performance thing. We don't have that power to do that. And therefore for the Russell Tribunal, there's almost no other way to approach it. I mean, there are things you can do, like Roger Waters concerts. You can change public opinion through music, through arts, through films, through, maybe, talk radio – there's different ways to get to the public. But, really, with complex issues like this, and an issue that needs to be framed in a way that

governments should be able to deal with it, human rights language, international law language, is almost the only thing you have. It's not good – like I say, it's pretty empty in a way in terms of enforcement – but that's really what you have. Unless we do a revolution, but we're not in a revolutionary moment these days. Revolutionary moments come and then you know, there is some – certainly in the anticolonial period in the 50s and the 60s, there was a window where anticolonial groups in the Global South could kind of rise up – but that was also limited, because once they got independence, the G7 got together and closed the whole system. They closed the UN, they moved the power from the General Assembly to the Security Council, they closed the IMF, and the World Bank, and the World Trade Organization to the Global South, so even though there was a window and some progress was made in terms of ending colonialism, very quickly the whole system closed down. So that's the problem: we have a system run by a few powerful governments that make their own rules. Israel is a perfect example of that. And then the question becomes, alright, but then how does civil society – it doesn't mean that we have to give up – it just means we have to have good strategies in terms of how we bring a just peace to Palestine/Israel.

And there we got a lot of inspiration from the ANC in South Africa. They faced kind of the same thing – a hostile international community, Thatcher called them terrorists, a hostile government, a white society that was not going to dismantle apartheid, international law wasn't very effective – they worked out complex strategies combining the military, combining moral stances like Mandela staying in jail all those years even if he could've gotten out earlier if he made deals, boycotts, appeals to international law – there were all kinds of strategies that we can use. And they won, in a way. They won politically, but they didn't win economically because the IMF and the World Bank made South Africa, until today, pay for all the debts of the apartheid regime. They didn't have the money, and they weren't allowed to distribute land to poor people, they had limitations on what they could do. So we live in a neocolonial world,

and that's why when I'm writing I'm always putting Palestine – and I think, in a way, the Tribunal did that a little bit – within a wider global context, because this isn't just a local situation. And the whole issue of neoliberalism, how do we decolonize not only Israel and its occupation, but how do we decolonize the whole international system, and give people their voice back, and their power back, and let them into the system – those weren't issues that the Tribunal dealt with, of course, but I think that the Tribunal was a kind of expression of that kind of a search for how we can somehow make inroads in terms of influencing policy.

P: Yeah, and obviously the public dimension, doing that search in public with, on the one hand, accomplished figures, but on the other hand the audience, who ever that may be, was that an important aspect of the Tribunal?

JH: Yeah, that's right. I mean the three elements of the Tribunal were people of moral authority – Mairead Maguire, who won the Nobel Peace Prize, legal authorities like Michael Mansfield, political figures – and then, of course, a figure from the art world like Roger Waters was very involved in the Tribunal. And then you had the witnesses coming in – those that testified like me, from the ground – and then the audience was civil society, basically. And the idea was that groups would take this and then somehow move it forward. There wasn't really an operational part to it, and maybe there couldn't have been. Once the Tribunal ended and had its summary that was kind of the end of it. I don't know if it could have gone any farther than that.

P: We talked at the very beginning about political vision for Palestine, or what would be a quote-unquote solution look like, and if I'm not mistaken, you yourself, or ICAHD, have had an evolution in that respect over the years. As you understand it, was there an explicit or implicit political vision guiding the Tribunal?

JH: No, the Tribunal didn't go there. And it really couldn't go there. The whole issue of what the solution is, of what the program is, *has* to be one that the Palestinians articulate. And then

it has to be supported by critical Israelis like me – it couldn't be something that was forged from above, even by very respected figures. That has to come from the people. And ICAHD is very involved in that. We're a political organization, so we're working very much through the One Democratic State Campaign to formulate, with Palestinians, a political program. So that has to be done. But the Tribunal couldn't do that. It was political – well, there's always that tension between international law and human rights on the one side, and being political on the other side. Even Amnesty, or Human Rights Watch. They don't come out and say, "we're against occupation." They say, "occupation is legal under international law, but there are constraints in the Fourth Geneva Convention, and we're against these violations." But they can't say, "we're for a particular solution." Or "we're against this and for this." Because it goes beyond their mandate as a human rights organization. And that's why an organization like ours, which is political, has to take, and took from the Russell Tribunal. It took from the arguments that were brought up, it took the human rights language, it took up the details of the violations, and then we tried to put it into the political sphere, and say, not only is this illegal, but Israel shouldn't get away with it. But at the same time, it wasn't their job to come up with a solution. That's our job as political groups.

So, I think, it was very important in terms of affecting public opinion. Certainly, the Tribunal got the word apartheid out, and other issues, and so on. That kind of softens the ground for us. So when we do come out with a political program, the public will be more receptive to it, because they'll already know that there's apartheid. So it won't come out as some sort of accusation, like twenty or thirty years ago, when you'd say 'apartheid,' people would say 'woah! What are you talking about, Israel's not South Africa, you're accusing Jews' – you see, what the Russell Tribunal does is it kind of softens the ground, it makes the argument, and then when people are already thinking in these terms, then when a political program comes in and builds on that, people can shift to that and it makes sense to them. Like the one state idea, by

itself, seems terrible, because there's no Jewish state of Israel. But when you build this whole case against apartheid, the apartheid regime, and settler colonialism, and all of that, using international law as well, then all of a sudden the One State [sic] has a logic and a moral dimension that it wouldn't have had just by itself.

P: Yeah, the reason that I mentioned that was because the UN's accumulation of decisions, and rulings, and resolutions, and inquiries and stuff that the Tribunal took as a starting point has a political vision embedded within that. Obviously, the UN's official position is towards a two-state solution. So I kind of wonder whether or not, by not having – and I know, obviously, the intention not to impose something as an outsider, to defer to Palestinians first-and-foremost and also Israelis is important – but to me, not really having an explicit political vision meant automatically accepting the existing one that was kind of enshrined in the framework that's been put in place by the US and the UN.

JH: Well, obviously governments, through the UN as well, are political. They have plans, they have their positions, they have their policies, and so on. And they sanction if people don't go along with them. They're political in that sense. But that's where the UN is limited. That's the structure of it. Everything that comes before the UN has to go through the Security Council. The Security Council is controlled by the five permanent members, any one of which can veto. So in a sense, the UN has been structured in that way by the governments so that it isn't effective. Governments do not want to concede their sovereignty to some international organization. They'll never do that. And certainly not an organization that, in numbers, is dominated by the Global South. So in a way, it's politics but in a very bad faith sectarian kind of way. It isn't politics that really sincerely looks at an issue like Palestine and says "ok, this is the underlying thing, these are the problems, and these are the rules" and gets to a solution. The solution they got to was simply one that served the purposes of the powers that be including

the Zionists, which have much more clout within the international system than the Palestinians do. 75 years ago.

So that's the problem, they're political, but political in a sectarian way. We're trying to be political – I think the difference is that groups like ours, and the Russell Tribunal, are trying to be political, but in a way in which *justice*, and international law and human rights, and peace, and security, and all those things – sustainability, in an environmental sense as well – are up front. I mean they're the guiding principles. Governments can't do that. Governments, partly because they think that they have to defend their own territory and their own State, or their own interests, corporate interests, and so on, define politics in a completely different way, in terms of *realpolitik*. So there's two concepts of politics. And I think, in many ways, a lot of the public that vote – and that's how you change government policy – certainly on Palestine there's been a sea-shift and I think they're much more sympathetic to the Palestinian cause. So part of that strategy of the Russell Tribunal is to affect public opinion so it gets to a point where the politicians that are running governments, especially in the G7, say “we want to get re-elected, and we see that Palestine's an issue of concern to our constituents, it's a political issue, and we have to respond.” So we have to raise the Palestinian issue like South Africa was, to that point where people come to a town hall meeting in Iowa, and somebody stands up and says “what about Palestine.” If that happened, that would signal to politicians that “woah, maybe this is an issue.” I think it's starting to happen in certain realms. In other words, I guess we would have a concept of a politics of justice, without political clout, and governments have a concept of ‘political clout comes first. First we have to defend our national interests, and our corporate interests, and so on, of our ruling elites, and then we'll use the language of justice.’ But justice isn't really a consideration. International law really isn't a consideration for these powerful governments.

P: Could you describe whether the Tribunal had any kind of impact on you, led you to rethink things, maybe you learned something from it?

JH: Well I learned things, obviously I learned things from different perspectives. Certainly the corporate part, I didn't know as much. And then just hearing from voices like Russell Means, the Native American movement, and other indigenous voices – that was very good. And I think that this was a good part of what the Tribunal did, it tried to connect dots. It tried to connect the dots of international law and politics, it tried to connect dots between these issues – corporate responsibility, government responsibility, and what's happening in Palestine – and it tried to connect the dots in terms of local-global. In other words, Palestinians in some ways are in the same situation as Native Americans, or migrants. The whole issue of how the system of international politics and corporate rule is affected the poor people of the world and the vulnerable people – I think that was certainly at the last part of the conference in New York especially. That's something they might have emphasized a bit more at the end. In other words, they're not going to come up with a plan. But there could have been – I don't know, maybe the Tribunal could have gone and tried to organize some kind of a follow-up of struggles in different parts of the world. Different kinds of struggles, and try to build on what they did at the last session, and really try to have a more structured and permanent form of communication. That could've been done, and that's something that I've been working on as well. I think there were attempts that didn't happen for some reason. I'm not sure exactly what they all are. But there was a website, and the website tried to keep it going... But there was an attempt to somehow keep this thing going... And that's the problem of course with civil society. We don't have resources. We don't have that organizational ability. And the left, to tell you the truth, is also a herd of cats. We don't work with each other very well, we're all siloed in our little issues, and that's also a problem.

P: I just had one more question: could you reflect on what the legacy of the Tribunal was in your view, and what it offered to civil society and the Palestinian movement?

JH: Well I guess it's legacy was that it was one of the stepping stones towards really bringing Palestine into the human rights and international law discussion and discourse. Really clarifying what the issues are in international law, and then just feeding into the public discussion, public consciousness raising, and so on. I don't think it had a lasting impact beyond that. There's a lot of initiatives that have done that as well. But it's played its role. I mean I don't think it had a huge impact per se, but it contributed.

P: Ok, and I just had one more question: is there anything else about the Tribunal that you thought was worth mentioning, any particularly memorable experiences?

JH: Well I think one of the useful things as well, certainly for me, was the networking. A lot of us can be very isolated here. Israelis and Palestinians can't always get together. But in terms of linking to other struggles, in terms of getting the input of international lawyers, linking up with a bigger body of supporters, *that* we're very limited in. So from the point of view of breaking our isolation, getting us in contact with others, the whole networking – you know, because these sessions were over two, three, four days. You're in hotels, you're going out for meals, you're hanging around, so it's really a good chance – when am I going to hang out with Russell Means, or Michael Mansfield? I know some of the people obviously but there were a lot of people I never knew, I didn't know. And then of course there was the follow-up that comes out of that. So that helped me a lot, I still have contacts from that time.

And part of it also is that it served as a legitimization. We're a small group, ICAHD. All the other groups are fairly limited as well. So the fact that it gave us a certain visibility, a certain celebrity, even, within our little tiny circles, so that, after, when we spoke about issues, it maybe had more of a resonance. It helped build our reputation as people that know what

they're talking about, that are politically more effective. So in terms of empowering us, being a part of that process, and interacting with those people, was important. Grassroots groups really are very isolated. That's something we struggle with. That's one way that the Tribunal stood out, more than a conference: at a conference everyone comes and gives a paper and goes home. One word I would use is that it was much more collaborative. And that was very useful. It was collaborative in the sense that we had a lot of people sitting down together, the jury, the witnesses, the organizers, really planning it all out and so on. That was really good. And collaborative in the sense of linking us all up and spending time with each other. A lot happens outside of the conference hall. Even who you're sitting with when the session is on, all that's really significant, every academic will tell you. 90% of the value of an academic conference is what happens outside of the session. Most academic meetings, you don't learn much usually. But it's networking. Which is one of the things that the Tribunal did very well, because it was over a few days, and in different parts of the world.

P: And do you see this as folding into your earlier point about trying to sustain, to keep it going a little bit afterwards and to try to make sure that that strengthening of a network of activists doesn't deteriorate again once it's all over?

JH: That didn't happen. I don't know why. The left really isn't good at that... people are activists, they're part time, they have their lives, they have other things to do, everybody's local issue takes all their time... so you don't have a lot of mental space for dealing with other issues, or organizing. And beyond that, I'm really concerned about systemic change – decolonization of the whole international system, for example – and not many people are really into that. And one of the problems really is – and this is something also that was another collaborative element to the Russell Tribunal – is that there's a real disconnect between the academic world and the activist world. Academics really have knowledge, they've got concepts, they can analyse, which is really important. I'm an academic, so I have those skills that most activists don't have.

Activists aren't academics. But the academics are limited because it's a body of theory, they only talk to each other, and they don't know what's happening on the ground. That's not their agenda. Their agenda is to write books and do theory. And then the activists, on the other hand, really know what's happening on the ground, but they don't have those concepts, they have trouble analysing. And so what I've been trying to do – and the Russell Tribunal... it did bring together activists, academics, and professional people, and that enabled a conversation to happen that doesn't happen usually. And that was useful. All that stuff that I was working on, there's little interest in it from the left. We're... a fucked up community, what can I tell you.

Interview, Bina Ahmad, July 12, 2023

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P: I was wondering if you could tell me more about the Tribunal, how you came to be involved, and what you did.

B: Sure. That can be a long or a short answer. The short answer is that I've been doing Palestine human rights work my whole life and I've worked pretty closely with Noura Erakat and other lawyers in the field. And so when the Tribunal was being formed, Noura specifically invited me to be part of the small legal team given not only my Palestine solidarity and organizing work, but my legal work in Palestine, my international human rights work. And so it fit very well with what the Tribunal was both politically and legally looking at.

The longer answer is that I've been doing Palestinian human rights work my whole life. I'm not Palestinian, I'm of Pakistani descent. My family is Ahmadi Muslim, a religiously-persecuted sect in Islam. And so, growing up with that ethos of understanding the most basic human rights and not having a home or homeland, being persecuted, not having a safe place, and what it feels like especially to experience state violence and power, is really what brought me to this work. So that's sort of why I do the work that I do, whether it's Palestine, international human rights, criminal defence, animal rights. So that general framework of who I am politically and as a lawyer is how I was brought into the Tribunal.

P: And as a member of the legal team for the New York session – I believe, correct?

B: Yeah.

P: And that was the only session that you were involved in?

B: It was. I believe I was invited to be part of another international session, I think I just couldn't make it work. And I apologize, I know there was like four sessions and I forget – I don't think it was the one in South Africa, it might have been London. But New York was the only one that I was involved in.

P: And what did that involvement consist in? Could you tell me a bit more about that?

B: Sure. The structure of the Tribunal – I think that it was one of the first of its kind as a peoples' tribunal, at least that I had seen – I think it really took seriously what that means. It's not just another sort of panel or another sort of discussion that we have on Palestine. It was almost like a mock trial, like a public trial, if you think of the Hague or these broad, large international platforms on genocide and human rights violations, like Nuremberg and what not, but here without the defendants: to have a body of experts who present evidence to the jury and to the public. So these are political thinkers, legal experts and scholars like Ben White and other folks who were invited to speak, who would then present to the jury, and the jurors are made up of other scholars and experts in general, in social justice human rights work – Angela Davis, Alice Walker, Dennis Banks – many other really powerful folks – Roger Waters, a couple other folks. They would be the jury to receive and hear the evidence that was publicly presented, preside over it, and then decide whether the evidence met these legal elements of different human rights violations under international human rights law principles. And us as the small legal team – it was myself, Noura Erakat, and two other European lawyers – we were then the small team who helped put together the legal analysis for the jury. We sat through the entire process of the experts presenting the evidence, the jury hearing it, and everybody discussing and deliberating it. And then, at the end, being with the jury as they wrote up their findings, we analyzed it and provided the legal framework as the legal experts for what we thought were the elements that were met to prove that these were international human rights violations by the Israeli government.

P: And, in New York, I assume that you also addressed the UN's responsibility. It was not just the Israeli government's violations, right?

B: Yeah, absolutely. So there's a couple layers here. We discussed the UN in terms of the principles, the international human rights bodies of humanitarian and human rights law are sort of housed within the UN – they obviously apply broadly outside of the governing body of the UN, but all of them are proliferated through the UN, there's different monitoring agencies through the UN. So, using those reports or analyses or treaties or rules of law from the UN to analyze this body of work, these human rights violations. Then there's the failing of the UN to do, really, anything that it proclaims to do. And of course, Israel is the massive human rights violator and committer of genocide and human rights violations, but there's so much complicity, of course, with the US, and support within the UN, which holds itself up as this international human rights protector body, which it really, sadly is not.

P: Did you or the legal team in general have a say in what the topics of the session would be and how they would be addressed? Or did the organizers come with the topics already pre-selected and you were just asked to give the jury the necessary legal knowledge and help them draft the conclusions?

B: My memory isn't the most fresh on that, but what I believe happened was we as the legal team did not select, or I don't remember us selecting, experts to present some kind of evidence on property destruction, or settlement expansion, or targeting of children, or anything like that. I think that was already baked into and organized within the Tribunal. Maybe Noura was part of that, I wasn't, I maybe came on later after the Tribunal was already planned and in the works, I wasn't part of the actual planning of it. But yeah, I don't recall us selecting who or what evidence would be presented. I think it was more us guiding the jury on different principles that we can analyze this with, like this is a violation of the Convention against Torture, or the

Declaration of Human Rights' principle of freedom of movement and family unification, and things like that, that's what the legal analysis is for. But I don't think that we actually selected what or who would be presented.

P: I just wanted to go back to – earlier you mentioned the peoples' tribunal format. Could you tell me more about what you understand the appeal of the peoples' tribunal format to be? You mentioned it in comparison to other conferences and stuff, so what could it do in comparison to other forms of protest or education?

B: Sure. I love the peoples' tribunal concept and the way that the Russell Tribunal did it in particular. I think that the way that it's evolved, people might just say, "we're going to have a peoples' tribunal," but it's just another panel on Palestine – I know people want to have as many different kinds of advocacy as they can on Palestine – but a tribunal I think is a very specific structure, and I think it's important to stick to that because it provides a lot of powerful tools. So unlike a panel where you can just choose speakers and they can talk about whatever topic you give them and have a discussion, a tribunal is much more structured and, I think, much more in-depth. The Russell Tribunal was several days. It doesn't have to be like that, but the principle is that it should be kind of like a mock trial, where there is extensive evidence presented, and it's by scholars – and of course you give your opinion and your take on things – but it's really about presenting verified data and evidence from your expertise, and presenting it in a form that is thorough and can be analyzed and is not just a couple statements or what not. And then to present it to a jury of people who will then hear it and see where that fits in, like "what are these violations of?" And then there's a separate third body of us, a small body of legal scholars, who are there to have heard the evidence, we were there throughout the Tribunal, using our legal expertise to say "these are all the various international laws that this conduct violates, and it can violate many different conventions and treaties." And I think that's really important as it's very thorough and it guides the process fully from the presentation of

very thorough evidence and data to a jury that's actually going to take each part and look at it, and to a group of legal experts that help plug in where these pieces of evidence fall, what international principles they violate and how. So it's either like a mock trial, or a live version of a very in-depth legal brief, I guess you could say, that has to be very in-depth and thorough and documented, and you have to show your evidence, and apply it to the law, and give your conclusion, and present a written conclusion, which the Tribunal also did. I definitely have critiques of the law in general, as a concept, which we can get to, but I think for that purpose, it gives a very deep historical, legal, and political record that I think panels can often skip over. Panels – and I've spoken on dozens of panels – they have a very important place in our legal and political organizing. But I think tribunals, perhaps, I would argue, reach a broader framework of folks who perhaps are more, maybe, within the very typical lawyer-brain of really wanting to see the evidence, not wanting just your opinions, really wanting to see what's actually happening, how does this apply under the law, what are the findings – approach it like a lawyer, a scholar who really wants to do all their background research. So, I think that these tribunals give that. And they give and create this historical record that we can look back to, which you're looking back to now, which is so thorough and long and in-depth, that is part of a peoples' record. It's not part of the failures of the UN and these UN reports that really go nowhere. It's not within this overly formal legal structure where the law, which I have many critiques of, can be incredibly restrictive and is not actually trying to find justice, it's really just trying to apply these laws that have been enacted by various powerful actors. But the peoples' tribunal can look at these situations and actually take a broad step back and not just be confined with, “well, politically, the UN, we don't want to call things genocide, so we're going to stay where we are.” Whereas the Tribunal can take in all of that and say, “we're not shy politically like the UN is, we can also be radical with the law and not be conservative in the way that many people don't want to fully condemn Israel and we can do that. We're not constrained by the

way that formal courts, or formal international legal bodies often are.” And I think all these things, especially now, ten, fifteen years on from the Tribunal, give me an even bigger appreciation of what it has created, the record it has created, and the model that it can set, that I think is now a really deep part of the record of our legal and political organizing on this.

P: That’s really helpful, thank you... you mentioned your critiques of law, I was wondering if you could tell me a little more about what those are for you, and in hindsight and in your view, how the Tribunal addressed or didn’t address some of the critiques that you have.

B: I could go on for hours, so I will try to keep it short. I’ve been a lawyer since 2005, so I’ve had a lot of years to reflect on this and go deep into my politics on this. I don’t feel like I’m a typical lawyer, I didn’t go to law school because I believe in the law. And I don’t think that, especially in the US, the legal system will give us justice. I went to law school because I view legal systems, particularly within the US – many legal systems around the world but particularly the US – as colonial systems and the systems of occupiers. My family is Pakistani, and my dad and grandparents grew up under the British occupation of India. And so, when South Asians were living under occupation under the British, they had to learn English, not because they wanted to, or because it was prestigious, but because they had to to survive and to understand their colonizers’ language, and what was being done to them, and how to fight back. It’s very similar to Palestinians, many speak Hebrew because they have to understand what their occupier and oppressor is saying and doing in order to fight back. And there are many Palestinians who are Israeli citizens and who have become licensed in Israeli legal systems as lawyers and fight in Israeli courts for human rights. That analysis really helps me, because that’s how I view the US legal system. I did not become a lawyer because I thought it was prestigious. As a person of colour, as a Muslim woman, as an Ahmadi woman, an Ahmadi Muslim woman, and someone who has radical politics, I have seen, and also, of course experienced, the violence of the US legal system. And there’s so much there. Having that

analysis really helps me be able to say – and many lawyers don't – that this is a colonial system. It's not a system that has been created by indigenous peoples, it's been created to decimate and eradicate indigenous peoples, to justify slavery and to justify property ownership of human beings and animals, but then with a veneer of neutrality and professionalism that makes it much harder to call out as a form of violence. For instance, I do a lot of work on prosecutor misconduct. And that is harder to call out for many people, including lawyers. It's not like police violence, that is a very spectacular flash of violence by someone who's not a lawyer or a judge. It's much harder for lawyers and other professionals to wrap their heads around the fact that our formalistic systems are also formalized forms of violence. Prosecutors commit violence every day. Judges are law enforcement. Our US legal system is a way to enforce white supremacist capitalism with this veneer of neutrality, professionalism, and this 'ordained by God' sort of approach.

So for me, that's how I always approach the law. I think many lawyers, especially when you go to law school, get really indoctrinated into – even if you go in with radical politics, it's really hard to not get indoctrinated with, "oh but this is the rule, this is the principle, and this is the avenue through the law that we have to go through to get justice." I think it's really hard to fight back and say, "this is just a tool in my toolbox." I don't actually think you can have justice in an apartheid and colonial system. Mandela was a lawyer under apartheid, which many people don't even know. I think it's just one weapon that you have to push back and that we have to step outside the law and realize that justice doesn't come from the law. It comes from peoples' organizing and it comes from uprising and revolutions. The law is just one component, and often a negative and oppressive component within that. So that's my view of the US legal system. I think the UN international human rights principles are also very similar. There are many really noble principles that we cite to all the time for human rights, but if we take a step back and look at the creation of the UN post-WW2 by the most powerful nations who won this

global war, setting up this system that's not actually democratic – the Security Council is *not* democratic, it's just permanent members who rule over everybody else in the world, have final say on everything, that are actually binding resolutions unlike the General Assembly, and create these principles – we have to take a step back and recognize that operating within this incredibly bureaucratic, incredibly powerful nation-state-built institution is not going to bring us revolution or liberation. It's just a system we're also stuck in and have to understand. But to just take a step back with that and not overly praise it when we get a good ruling, like “yes, this is justice” or, if you succeed as a lawyer, people kind of get an ego, like “now I'm a great person and smart because I'm a good lawyer that won within this system.” And so I want lawyers and people to take that critical view of the law, whether it's US or international law, and recognize that we can be so much more radical and creative than what the law gives us. And we don't have to confine our minds to, “well this is what the law says.” We can understand what the law says but also say “well this is also just messed up.” International law is often just the law of war. It doesn't say war is illegal – even occupation, the way you conduct an occupation, is what international law tells you to do. It doesn't say that it's completely unjust.

So within the Tribunal, sorry this is a long answer getting to that, we didn't really have the space, and maybe a lot of us didn't have those politics of wanting to take a step back – or maybe they did but I don't think there was a space created – just even having to use these international human rights principles, that shouldn't limit us in being able to call out all of the different forms of violence by the UN and by Israel. And I think it often does. Because we're confined into writing a legal brief and doing a legal analysis. So the Tribunal didn't have that space, and I think that was lacking, being able to say these critiques, like “we don't need the UN or other powerful actors and nation-states to tell us what's right and wrong, and what's right and wrong with what's being done to us, *we know it*. And we can say whatever we want, and the law shouldn't confine us.” So I do think that that wasn't there, but I think that if we

were ever to revisit it, I think that there's definitely a more radical political shift within the legal community that means that maybe there would be a space now if we were to do it again.

P: One thing that was interesting for me, looking at the conclusions, was that there were lots of presentations that went back further than 1967, whether it was Ilan Pappé, or Ben White, or others. And, the Tribunal actually talked about 1948, how the UN actually legitimized the State of Israel, and so on. But then what was interesting for me was that, in the conclusions of the document that was put out, and in the recommendations, that part was lost a bit. The final judgment was kind of just saying, "the UN has failed to implement its resolutions since 1967," but didn't really draw any real implications from the presentations that talked about the UN before 1967. So I was just wondering if you could comment on that a bit.

B: Yeah – and I wish that my memory was better on how that came to be in the final findings – but I think it's also just that organizing a radical politics is an ever-evolving thing for many people, and I think that a lot of folks who are in social justice spaces including in Palestine spaces, obviously care about Palestine and care about human rights, but not everyone has the same radical politics overall. You know, I'm an anarchist, I'm an abolitionist, I don't believe in nation-states, I don't believe in those power structures. And that's also antithetical to being a lawyer in many ways. And so many people don't have that. And so, sort of like I was saying before, they kind of do cling to – or just are really confined with the way that they think to needing to see what the law says. And that's what the final finding is. That's what the final say is. Because there were actors from around the globe and around the movement as a whole, beyond lawyers or what not, taking part. So it had to be findings that the jury came to as a group and agreed to. And I think, especially where Palestine organizing was back then, it is incredible to see how much more radical and outspoken it's become. Even growing up, you couldn't even say Palestine, I remember, or really even talk about 1948 or just the illegitimacy of that entire process in general. I think that's definitely shifted to where people now do. And I

remember talking to people who did confine themselves to '67, and the Green Line, and that was always really depressing, because it was so limiting. And I think that people – even [inaudible] ten, fifteen years ago – I think people were kind of stuck there, like, “well that’s what the international community has agreed. So at least we can all agree on the '67 borders, right?” And I think, now, people have shifted and pushed it more, saying, “we don’t have to be confined to that. We can go back to '48, we can go back to Ottoman rule and British occupation, we can really talk about the formal long-term violence that’s taken place in Palestine.” I don’t know if that was definitely the case then, and I also don’t think that the legal community particularly, or necessarily all scholars, let’s say, were there – because it was a more risky thing to do, especially ten or fifteen years ago, to talk about '48 and the illegitimacy of Israel as a whole, or the UN as a whole. I think that’s more accepted now, or at least not as controversial a thing to say. And you’re always restricted to what the group decides. I forget how many jurors there were, but there were a *lot*. There were at least ten to fifteen, I think, and so it’s hard to come to consensus, I think, with everyone on that.

P: That’s helpful, too, because I was like ten or thirteen when this happened so I can’t really – you know, it might be shocking to you...

B: Oh my god! [laughs]

P: I didn’t really have a sense of what the state of the discussion was in, let’s say, North America and Europe was then. I’m very much someone who came of age and learned about Palestine end of the 2010s up to now. So I would say it’s very different for me.

Some of the people I spoke to mentioned how generation played a role in how people who were involved approached Palestine or what their politics were. Was that also a sense that you had, and if so, what are your thoughts on that? Maybe it’s not phrased very well...

B: I just want to make sure I understand, you're asking about the intergenerational influence on Palestine organizing?

P: Yeah, like whether there were intergenerational differences among jury members, presenters, and anyone involved in the Tribunal in general.

B: For sure. I think, whether it was the Tribunal or in general, there'll always be generational differences. People come with their own long history of doing this work, or trauma having done this work, and been subjected to the violence if they're Palestinian. So that, I think is definitely different. I also think that, in general, whether this Tribunal or outside it, people who have been in the legal world and lawyers, whether it was the jurors or the small legal team, who've been legal actors for a long time – I think that, slowly, that system just kind of indoctrinates you. I have very radical elder mentors who I deeply love and respect. But, you know, the vast majority of lawyers, especially older lawyers, are a little bit more conservative in terms of the analysis about the law, and needing to be careful, and staying within these legal frameworks, and being respected as a lawyer. I think that's definitely different for me and definitely this next generation of lawyers. And still for me, when I went to law school, I graduated in '05, it was still really controversial to talk about Palestine, to talk about abolition, to be an anarchist – and now it's incredible to talk to law students who are like, “abolition's just part of the lexicon.” Talking about the US legal system being a system of white supremacy, an illegitimate system, is very much, like, common now. Which is wonderfully shocking to me because that was not at all how it was when I was in law school. And so I do think that there were, in general, generational shifts that happened with organizing and movements, and I think for sure within the Tribunal. There's also just the radical actors like Angela Davis – who will always be a hero of mine, she always has politics that I follow and hone in on and she's such an incredible thinker – I think she definitely has maintained and always pushed for radical politics. And I think other folks – it's easy to just get within your own world, or also be stuck where your generation of

organizing was, and I think many people find it hard to pass the baton on to the next generation and learn from them. We don't often have that concept of learning from the younger generation, it's like they should learn from us, which I think they should, but we definitely should learn from the younger generation because that's how movements work. You pass that baton and they need to do it better than you did, every time. And that's also just hard for folks to accept and break their minds open to.

P: Another question I had was about this idea of complicity, or even criminal complicity that the Tribunal was getting at. In the New York session, and also in London and Barcelona, there was an attempt to, as far as I understand, to set out a legal argument for why a particular State or organization is legally responsible for being complicit. I guess I was wondering what, in your understanding, the Tribunal thought it would achieve by coming to this determination and putting it out there.

B: Do you mean in terms of condemning certain actors for committing these violations? Sorry, can you clarify what you're getting at?

P: Yeah, like what the strategy was, or what the aim was in doing so. Was it like a name-and-shame thing, hoping that it would raise awareness among ordinary people living in those countries, or did they think it would move government officials into action, or...

B: Yeah, that's also just a big question – naming-and-shaming, why we do it, does it work, is it good – for movements. I think for sure, naming – and in a very formalistic, technical way, like I was saying about the Tribunal creating this historical scholarly record of “here's the evidence, here are the rules of law.” Applying it, applying these basic rules and you're violating them – I think, for sure, is a shaming mechanism, because obviously it doesn't have any sort of legal enforcement capabilities or any sort of precedent-holding within larger legal systems or formal systems. So I think the shaming aspect of it is definitely key. I also think that creating

this historical record that we can also cite to is also part of it. Because, like I was saying with panels – they’re great, I love being on panels – but they don’t create this scholarly historical record that somebody like you, for instance, could cite back to, right? The Tribunal was so formal, and detailed, and in-depth, that you can actually cite back to it in your future scholarly work, in your future research work. You can actually cite to the findings. And that’s hard to do with other panels that aren’t aiming to create a historical record. I think the tribunal part of it *is* to create this record, that otherwise may not be there. And we don’t always think about that when we’re in the moment doing our work. I think that’s definitely part of it, to hopefully also give ammunition to folks doing this work – that when you cite different scholarly articles, or legal findings, you can also cite to the Tribunal. It was very in-depth and very formal, and hopefully something that scholars will actually find legitimate to cite to.

And the calling out and naming-and-shaming, I think, is always important, whether we think it does anything or not. As a lawyer, I can definitely tell you that I think that the larger political outcry in shaming has so much more force than the law. And it’s so depressing to say that. For instance, people think about, and I grew up thinking that *Brown v. Board* desegregated schools – and later you realize that it wasn’t the case. It was hundreds of thousands of people putting their lives on the line and dying and being subjected to violence for decades that got us to that point. And it’s the public outcry and amplifying this through the international stage, what was happening in the US, that pushed the legal system to finally follow and change. And that’s frustrating, because even when there’s legal findings – you know, there’s a rule, obviously you’re not supposed to discriminate in hiring for instance in the US – it happens all the time. And there’s really no accountability, even though that’s been illegal for decades, there’s no accountability until there’s a larger public outcry or movement around it, and shaming. So actually, I’ve grown to appreciate that even more and think that it has so much more weight than we originally thought that it did, especially being a disillusioned lawyer and realizing that

I can cite to any legal rules and statutes and cases all I want, but it doesn't actually change things until there's a movement and public outcry along with it.

P: In your understanding, was it an explicit goal of the Tribunal to help build that movement? Was there an attempt to get people more educated and involved and mobilized for Palestine liberation?

B: I don't know if we explicitly thought of ourselves as creating a historical record for the future – I mean, obviously, looking back, that's what we did. I think, for sure, a goal was to amplify what was happening, to reach people who also were maybe more on the fence and not necessarily involved in the movement, and also grabbing the movement and lifting it up, and unifying it, and bringing folks together. It was enormous. So many people came, there was so much coverage. International actors came and there was coverage all over the world about it. I think that definitely helped amplify the struggle and what we're talking about. I think it helped to bring folks to this movement and to actually galvanize folks to organize together more or do something more based on this fire that was lit. So I do definitely think that's always a part of why we do what we do. To amplify the movement, amplify the cause, bring folks together. Because often times – I've written reports for the UN, and it's not like I have any illusions that that's going to change anything – it's more that that coverage of the report, or being at a panel talking about it, is more the ultimate goal. Which is kind of true of lawsuits and legal avenues in general, too.

P: With regards to talking about the fact that, lots of times, mass movements are actually the ones that create more pressure for change than just a naming-and-shaming campaign or just like one legal determination – in a lot of the Tribunal's reports, at the very end, there's a recommendation for quote-unquote civil society to implement BDS, it's usually just one statement. Can you speak to the relationship between the Tribunal and the BDS movement?

Just maybe how you understand the relationship and whether there were any discussions about what relationship the Tribunal should have to BDS?

B: I don't remember any explicit conversations about how the Tribunal should relate to BDS. I think in general, BDS, even before it was launched as a movement in like 2005 or something, was always just part of what people did – boycotting Israeli goods, boycotting supporting Israeli organizations – and that goes back to centuries of organizing and following the South African apartheid struggle boycott as well. So I think that's always a part of our organizing and our work. BDS was launched – and the SJPs and all that – I think around 2005. I didn't benefit from those, I had graduated by then. I think it sort of formalized and put onto a larger stage this principle that people often operate with. I'm an animal rights activist, I'll boycott companies that test on animals, I don't buy meat or dairy – and that's just something that we do. But I think formalizing it into a campaign called BDS with SJPs – and this is how we get it across the country and across the world – definitely amplified the struggle. Not only just the tactic of, “we want to boycott, what companies are complicit in this and what do they do,” but also, “why are we doing this.” I think that definitely is always a part of the organizing, but I think BDS, especially, formalized that and made it an explicit tactic and goal within the movement. So I don't necessarily know that we explicitly talked about that, I think for me it's always a part of the fabric of what we do in organizing.

P: I wanted to also ask about whether, as you understood it, the Tribunal had any political program for Palestine. I think it's fair to say that it was more of a solidarity initiative than something run by Palestinians, which I think might have some implications – but did it have a political program for Palestine, and would you have any reflection on that?

B: Yeah, I think Palestinians were definitely involved in organizing and creating it – it wasn't fully launched out of Palestine or just Palestinian organizations – initially it was definitely a

solidarity measure. But I think the political programming and formatting of it was definitely important— the thing about tribunals is that it's not neutral. You're not going in like, "what are we going to find!" It's like, "we know what we want to call out and find, we're just going to do it in this way." We already know what politics we're approaching it with, so it's not like we had any soft Zionists or anything. There was definitely a very clear political angle, which I think is really powerful. You know, part of gathering hundreds of people from around the world to come together is just creating that space. We had a lot of events after, a lot of political events, like Dennis Banks, Angela Davis, and Alice Walker spoke at these events after the days of the Tribunal. Each night we would have a political gathering, or just like a party or something. And I think just creating that space, like "this is a space for Palestinian activists and for Palestinians, and it's a safe place where we have the same politics and we're trying to do something about this issue" was definitely a part of it. I get frustrated with conferences sometimes, it's just that you don't have a lot of time to connect to people, you go to a panel, you don't really learn anything – but I think the real value of conferences is where you get those moments to connect and actually hang out with people, and talk to them at the after-party or after-gathering or what not – that's where you build more of those connections, and so much comes out of it, that I think that was definitely a result and also a goal. Just sort of to create that space and get people to connect and have those politics and organize off of that based on the Tribunal.

P: Would it be fair to say that having those sustained four or five day sessions where you have a lot of pro-Palestine activists in a room together for a period of time allowed you to go deeper into some of those conversations outside of the formal structure of the Tribunal in a way that was informative or helpful?

B: 100%. I think, obviously the findings of the Tribunal and the processes of it was history-making, it wasn't really done before, making this record. But I think that so much of what people remember and what people got out of it is not necessarily – the findings are great, but

it's not necessarily that we're going to hold up the findings and go, "this was a moment-" – it's more that people gathered and met other people from other countries who were doing this work that we'd never heard of, and either got to start organizing together out of that, or created other little branches of organizing or organizations out of that. And I think that's huge, and perhaps even the bigger part of this. I don't hesitate to say that I'm very proud of the Tribunal, and I love it, and I'm very glad about what we did. But I think the longer-lasting impact of so many of these efforts is not the formal goal. The goal is to come up with findings, to analyse this, but it's really, like, creating these spaces that launch people. It sparks people to work together, they're able to have longer lasting relationships and organizing relationships that I think are the more powerful, longer-lasting impacts of these things. I think even of lawsuits and other sorts of legal endeavours, whether they are a tribunal or something else, the more powerful part is the people coming together, and being drawn together by this, and moving forward with their relationships and political conversations from that. I think that's actually the more powerful takeaway for me.

P: This is maybe a hypothetical question, and maybe I'm asking you to speculate a bit – but could the Tribunal maybe have done more to try to keep the network and the relationships that were formed going? I know obviously there were limitations of money, and everyone's busy and everything...

B: Yeah, for sure. I mean, in hindsight, there's always better things that you can do, and I think – especially when you're doing a Tribunal, it's so data and legal and writing-intensive, and evidence-intensive – it's not just a one-day panel, it's a very detailed and in-depth endeavour. It's very heavy. I think it is easy to sort of lose sight or to not necessarily realize that something else that you should do, in addition to creating this record, is to keep things going, whether, every two years, another conference, even if it's virtual or what not, or if it's just trying to gather people together and reflect on it or see where people are, and keep that momentum

going, I think that's often just a failing within the left and legal movements, in not doing that. Not having the foresight, and only later do you realize that so many things came out of a conference, and maybe it could have been even more powerful if we had uplifted them or encouraged them to keep things going. So I think that's definitely a critique of the Tribunal and many other leftist efforts but yeah, that's a very important point to raise.

P: And maybe following up on that, if you were to imagine having the Tribunal again today, what would it look like to you? Is there anything that you think it might do differently, either because of the contemporary moment or for other reasons?

B: Yeah, I think there's always things you look back on and want to do differently or better based on hindsight and what you wouldn't have known at the time. But I think what we were talking about of intentionally following up on and keeping the momentum going, keeping people connected and coming together – whether it's just check-ins, or a follow-up conference, or having lists or groups or just something of people who are now connected here so that we can all keep the connection going. That's one thing I would do. Definitely just bringing a more radical politics in, the critique about having to use a legal system in general that's not created by people but created by nation-states and powerful victors of war, really. Like, “what does that mean? And we don't want to confine ourselves to that.” And maybe also being very intentional about creating a historical record – “what does that mean and what can it serve down the line?” I think we did a great job of creating a historical record but I think that at the time I wasn't thinking of it like that. There was so much happening, and so much work that I was like, “I just got to get through this, and analyze this,” and, you know, now, the fact that you found me and [anonymous] and all these other people, and you can follow up on that, and it's a record that you can look back at and that you want to look into, I think is really powerful. And yeah, just being more intentional about thinking outside the law, and focusing on the movement

organising, and the people connections, and the radical politics that can come out of this, I think that would be another thing I would probably do.

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